

Deliverable 3.1

Responsible DT indicators and metrics

The Framework Programme for Research & Innovation

ETAPAS

ETHICAL TECHNOLOGY ADOPTION IN PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION
SERVICES

Grant Agreement Number: 101004594

[H2020-SC6-TRANSFORMATIONS-2020] Socioeconomic and Cultural
Transformations in the context of the fourth industrial revolution

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List of definitions & abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CoC	Code of Conduct
D	Deliverable
DTs	Disruptive Technologies
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
H2020	Horizon 2020
PAs	Public Administrations
PS	Public Sector
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RDT	Responsible Disruptive Technologies
UC	Use Case
WP	Work Package

The ETAPAS Consortium consists of:

Logo	Organisation acronym and name	Country
	MEF – Ministero dell'Economia e delle Finanze	Italy
	Intellera – Intellera Consulting Srl	Italy
	2021.AI – 2021.AI APS	Denmark
	SINTEF – SINTEF AS	Norway
	PROKOM – Sem & Stenersen Prokom AS	Norway
	CERTH – Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis	Greece
	IIT – Fondazione Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia	Italy
	LC – The Lisbon Council for Economic Competitiveness ASBL	Belgium
	KTH – Kungliga Tekniska Hoegskolan	Sweden
	CEA – Commissariat à l'énergie atomique et aux énergies alternatives	France
	FDG – Fondazione Don Carlo Gnocchi Onlus	Italy
	MUKA – Municipality of Katerini	Greece
	UNIGRAZ – University of Graz	Austria
	KI – Karolinska Institutet	Sweden

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1. Executive Summary

Within the ETAPAS project – Ethical Technology Adoption in Public Administration Services – the conclusion of the **Research & Design** phase, which focuses on the definition of a Responsible Disruptive Technology (RDT) Framework, is marked by the development of the first version of the **RDT Indicators Framework**. Its main purpose is to enable an **ethical, social and legal assessment of DT applications within the public sector**. Such an assessment should **cover all the life cycle of the DTA** from its design toward to its ongoing monitoring and should **involve relevant stakeholders** when required (DTA owner, organisation management, developer, user, final user).

By combining **desk research, experimentations, co-designing and stakeholder engagement techniques**, we manage to develop a comprehensive Responsible DT Indicators Framework, which includes risk and mitigation indicators delivered in the form of a fact-based general checklist and automated or semi-automated computational indicators tailored to each ETAPAS use case.

The present report “**Responsible DT indicators and metrics**” aims at giving a detailed presentation of the **approach and structure of the framework**, and the **rationales** behind them, describing the methodology and process followed for its design and development, and at providing an overview description of both the assessment and computational indicators developed within the ETAPAS project so far. The RDT Indicators Framework will then be uploaded on a prototypical software platform, developed by 2021.AI within the project, to enable an easy undertaking of the assessment by public sector organisations. In the following project phase, both the framework and the platform will be tested and validated by applying them to the four ETAPAS real-life use cases, which focus on **AI, Robotics and Big/Open Data** enabled applications. Moreover, the present document presents the scoring system and describes how intermediate and final results of the assessment are determined, which also will be subject to testing and review in the **Test & Validation** phase of the project. Furthermore, the document outlines how we expect the results to be shown in the platform dashboards.

It should be noticed that this deliverable is complementary to two other deliverables, namely **D3.2 “Measurement Guidelines”** and **D3.3 “Validation method and guidelines”**. In particular, **D3.2 “Measurement Guidelines”** describes in detail the indicators, introducing related guidelines and recommendations, as well as the scoring methodology and provides all the information needed to correctly undertake the assessment. The method for the evaluation and tailoring of the principles, risks and set of indicators and metrics for the peculiarities of the context of application of each use case/DTA is covered, on the other hand, in **D3.3 “Validation method and guidelines”**.

As mentioned, the research findings presented in this report were also the result of numerous consultations with stakeholders and, in particular, with the public sector organisations which are part of the ETAPAS Consortium. According to our last consultation with the Consortium, the RDT Indicator Framework is clear and gives practical insights on how to mitigate the risks of DT adoption. We will continue the improvement process as planned and described in the final section of the document, where we outline **7 key areas for future development and research** for the improvement of the RDT Indicator Framework.

2. Introduction

ETAPAS project aims to improve public service delivery for citizens by facilitating the ethical adoption of Disruptive Technologies (DTs) by public sector organisations. The ethical adoption of DTs can, in fact, significantly improve not only the quality but also the reliability, speed and accessibility of services provided by public administrations and public service providers. Yet, the real impact of their adoption is largely unknown, so that deploying these disruptive technologies in public administrations requires a thorough assessment of their potential impact, benefits and risks for the delivery of public goods. In addition, most documents, reports, and literature focus on the private sector.

The public sector is affected by DTs both through its own use of these technologies, which it can largely control, and through the introduction of DTs outside its domain, which it can only control to a limited extent. Just like other parts of society, the public sector is subject to requirements of efficiency, which can justify the introduction of disruptive technologies. However, the public sector differs from private organisations in its legal status and its unique social role, which entails stringent obligations in terms of transparency, equity and accountability. For instance, citizens expect decisions on public services to be made by public officials who apply clearly specified criteria in a transparent and systematic manner, and they also expect such decisions to be appealable. Therefore, the application of DTs in public administration decision-making is subject to different and often stricter requirements and restrictions with respect to its application in the private sector.

Given its special role, the public sector deserves a wider approach to impact assessment for the adoption of DT applications. In this context, the ETAPAS challenge is to develop a wide framework capable of embracing the complexity of adopting DTs in PAs and their impact on the public good, so that each public sector organisation, takes into account the ethical, social, environmental and legal impacts from the conception to the design, implementation and application of the technology. With this aim, ETAPAS is co-designing with public bodies a comprehensive Responsible Disruptive Technologies (RDT) Framework consisting of ethical principles, an analysis of the legal framework, an overview of the ethical risks and social impact of DTs in the public sector and an ensuing RDT Indicators Framework to practically measure those risks and impacts. In particular, the aim of the Indicators Framework is to assess the risks and negative impacts of the adoption of a specific disruptive technology application by a public sector organisation, but also the effectiveness of potential mitigation actions to be implemented.

Different examples of indicator frameworks for the impact assessment of specific disruptive technologies, such as AI and Robotics, can be found in the literature, some of them making also special reference to the public sector. From the literature analysis and the aforementioned components of the RDT framework, ethical, social and legal aspects need to be considered. In particular, it should also focus on the consequences of human interaction with technology, both in terms of security and in terms of social implications. In addition, since we are dealing with the adoption of a DT application by a public sector organisation, inclusiveness, sustainability and impact on the work environment are also of great importance, as well as privacy and liability concerns. In general, the framework should take into account both quantitative and qualitative dimensions of the impact. Given the multiplicity of aspects to be taken into consideration and the various responsible figures in the process of developing and adopting a DT application, it is important to involve all the relevant stakeholders in the design and the subsequent implementation of the impact assessment.

Within the ETAPAS project, we developed the RDT framework in a fully participatory approach and we also foresee its testing and validation on four real-life use cases, namely:

- **UC1 - Ethically Responsible Big Open Data**, concerning the NoiPA platform by the Italian Ministry of Economy and Finance that offers HR shared services to around 100 Italian central and local public administrations;
- **UC2 - Robot-mediated rehabilitation**, dealing with a humanoid robot used for the assessment of patients' walking abilities;
- **UC3 - Municipality chatbot Kari**, regarding an AI-based virtual agent called Kari, that was adopted in more than 80 municipalities in Norway and Denmark to answer the citizen's questions on the municipality services;
- **UC4 - Public Organizations Multi-factor Misinformation Handling**, deals with the deployment of AI for fake news detection and prioritization of emerging issues in the municipality of Katerini (Greece).

Moreover, a prototypical software platform will be designed and developed in order to enable the ethical assessment of DTs in the public sector on the basis of the ETAPAS RDT framework. The prototypical platform will also be tested and refined during use cases implementation.

Finally, lessons learned from use cases implementation together with mitigation actions and improvements recommendations will feed into the final version of the RDT Framework and into the definition of the ETAPAS Governance Model for supporting PAs in DTs evaluation, development and adoption.

2.1. Purpose and scope of the document

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide a clear overview of the structure, methodology and process followed for the designing and developing the RDT Framework and a general description of both the assessment and computational indicators developed within the ETAPAS project. The indicators contained in the framework are functional to the ethical, social and legal assessment of the adoption of specific applications of disruptive technologies by organizations in the public sector. In particular, the present document should be read together with D3.2 and D3.3 and was defined as part of the activities of Task 3.1 "Indicators and metric definition".

A brief overview of the indicators structure and of the methodology used to develop the RDT indicators framework is available within the document together with the rationales and framework structure, while a very detailed description of the indicators, both assessment and computational ones, defined during this project phase as well as qualitative methodologies to tailor, interpret and use the RDT indicators to a specific DTA, the scoring system and guidelines for results' interpretation are presented within D3.2.

It should be noted that this document is to be read in conjunction with D3.3 which outlines the stakeholder validation methodology and that the present version **will then be reviewed in the "Test and Validation" phase of the project**, so as to be improved and validated.

2.2. Structure of the document

With the aim of accomplishing the goals outlined above, **Chapter 3** of the document first presents an overview of the entire RDT framework and then an overview of the RDT indicator framework. The Chapter closes with an analysis of the key insights from the RDT Indicator Framework.

The document continues with an overview description of the Assessment and Computational Indicators, outlined respectively in **Chapters 4 and 5**. Then, **Chapter 6** "Practical use of the RDT Indicator Framework", includes all explanations on how to complete the assessment, how the scores are calculated, and the results presented, as well as how to interpret the results. At this point, **Chapter 7** presents conclusions and a description of the areas where further research and development is needed. Finally, in **Annex 1** the best practices analysed for the development of the framework are presented, while **Annex 2** provides additional charts for a synthetic view of the RDT Framework and **Annex 3** reports the glossary we developed to accompany the Framework.

3. Overview of the RDT Indicator Framework

3.1. Overview of the RDT Framework

Figure 1: The three phases of the ETAPAS project

ETAPAS project implementation is structured in three phases as depicted in **Figure 1** above: Research & Design, Test & Validation, Synthesis & Impact pathways. The Research & Design phase is carried out within WP2 and WP3 and entails the definition of the Responsible Disruptive Technology (RDT) Framework. Defining and formalizing a conceptual Responsible Disruptive Technologies framework that allows to assess and govern the ethical risks of DT-based applications as well as identify potential social and legal impacts is a key objective of the ETAPAS project.

In particular, the ETAPAS RDT Framework is composed by:

- A generic **Code of Conduct** for the adoption of DTs in the Public Sector setting out 10 ethical principles;
- A **Legal Framework**, providing an analysis of the referring European legal framework;
- An overview of the **ethical risks and social impacts of DTs**, including an extensive mapping of risks and impacts;
- The **RDT indicators** to practically measure those risks and impacts.

Figure 2: The RDT Framework components

As **Figure 2** points out, each component of the framework builds upon the results of the preceding one. Also, many project deliverables are considered living documents in order to allow for their revision during project lifetime, ensure coherence and adherence to practical evidences.

As outlined, the first component of the framework is the “**ETAPAS Generic Code of Conduct**” for DTs in the public sector, which provides 10 ethical principles to guide public sector organisations while developing and adopting disruptive technologies. It can serve both as an affirmation of fundamental values and as the basis of an internal accountability mechanism for the organisations.

In its current version, the ETAPAS Code of Conduct considers the following key ethical principles:

1. Environmental sustainability;
2. Justice, equality, and the rule of law;
3. Transparency and explainability;
4. Responsibility and accountability;
5. Safety and security;
6. Privacy;
7. Building an ethical culture involving the employees;
8. Retaining human contacts;
9. Ethical public-private cooperation;
10. Continuous evaluation and improvement.

The second component is the “**European Legal Framework**”, which provides an overview of the legal landscape of Primary, Secondary and Case Law for DTs in the public sector. More specifically, it describes identified gaps in binding and non-binding sources regarding the regulation of DTs in the public sector, informs about potential regulatory solutions and provides guidelines for the assessment of legal aspects of DT-based applications.

The third component consists of the “**ETAPAS Risk Framework**”, which provides a detailed mapping of all the risks to which public bodies are exposed when adopting DTs. The Risk Framework is the result of a 4 steps analysis:

1. At first a thorough **literature review** was carried out based on different sources, both academic papers and grey literature, to study the ethical, social and legal issues of disruptive technologies adoption.
2. Secondly, we formalised our analysis into a **structured framework** that categorizes these risks by identifying commonalities, spotting potential contradiction among different sources and tailoring the results to the specific context of the public sector.
3. The Risk framework was then **reviewed and validated by the ETAPAS consortium partners** - and in particular the public sector organisations - for ensuring that the results were relevant and based on both research and practical experience.
4. In the final reworking of the framework, particular emphasis was put on **consistency** in the description of risks. As the term “risk” can be used to address both undesirable outcomes and causes of such outcomes, we decided to focus only on the undesirable outcomes to avoid the inclusion of fairly distant so-called root causes.

Figure 3 below synthetises the process followed for the development of the ETAPAS Risk Framework.

Figure 3: The process followed to develop the ETAPAS Risk framework

The ETAPAS Risk Framework in its current version identifies **35 risks and 8 risk categories** as follows:

1. **Risks concerning direct interaction with humans**, including the risks of physical and psychological harm;
2. **Legal Risk**, such as liability and law infringement risk;
3. **Governance risks**, which covers risks arising from mismanagement, weak supervision and lack of standard procedures;
4. **Enhanced inequality and discrimination**, which comprises all the risks related to possible perpetuation of discrimination with DT-based solution and the unequal access to and benefit from the DTs, due to economic, cultural and social differences;
5. **Errors and misuse**, such as risks emerging from the DT lack of robustness, biased performances or security branches, as well as the risk of the DT being used as autonomous weapon, for malicious surveillance purposes or for spreading disinformation while limiting the decision-making power of the citizens;
6. **Security and data protection risks**, including the risk of the DT being hacked to get information access or to change its behaviour;
7. **Unsustainable use**, including high level of energy consumption or wide use of environmentally unsustainable materials;
8. **Workplace issues**, stemming from job displacement and lack of competences by public sector employees.

It is worth noting that the Risk framework perfectly integrates with the other components of the RDT Framework. In fact, all the identified risks trace back to the 10 ethical principles of the ETAPAS Code of Conduct, due to the fact that when a risk realises, it usually means that an ethical principle was violated. For example, if an AI app is biased, it means that the principle of Justice, equality, and the rule of law was not respected.

The final component of the RDT Framework is the **ETAPAS RDT Indicators Framework** which provides a practical methodology to evaluate and assess the impact of the DT application as well as if and how the risks are mitigated. The Indicator Framework builds on all the previous components and it is the objective of this deliverable. Also, measurement guidelines are provided within this deliverable to enable public sector organisations to properly undertake the impact assessment of their DT application leveraging on the ETAPAS tools.

In the next project phase “Test & Validation¹”, the full RDT framework will be tested and validated on the four ETAPAS real-life use cases. This testing phase will inform both the development and refinement of the prototypical platform supporting the assessment and the refinement of the conceptual RDT framework. In the final phase of the project “Synthesis & Impact pathways” lesson learned from use cases implementation will be analysed and a Governance model will be designed aimed at managing, by design, the ethical risks throughout the life-cycle of a DT-based application and considering the social and legal aspects of DTs.

3.2. Methodology applied for the Indicator Framework

Figure 4: The methodology followed to develop the RDT Indicator Framework

As **Figure 4** illustrates, the theoretical basis for the construction of the ETAPAS indicator framework is to be found in the principles contained in the ETAPAS Code of Conduct, the ethical, social and legal risks identified by the ETAPAS Risk framework and the identified best practices from the literature. This theoretical basis was then complemented with a consultation with all ETAPAS consortium partners in order to refine and validate the approach and make the results relevant to the reality of the PA organisations.

In particular, the approach to the construction of the framework was identified through the analysis and comparison of best practices. **Annex 1** reports in details the identified best practices and describes the contribution each of the documents brought to the ETAPAS indicators framework. From the **literature and best practices**, it emerged that in addition to assessing the level of risk or ethical compliance to which a public sector organisation might be exposed once adopting a specific DT Application (DTA), it was essential to assess, given the fact that we are dealing with an emerging and changing area, the quality and effectiveness of any action put in place with the aim of mitigate such risks (i.e., mitigation actions). In addition, most of the frameworks analysed had a checklist-like structure, with many indicators consisting of single-answer questions. In the literature, many of the indicators are based on self-assessment. However, given the stringent socio-ethical requirements of the public sector, we felt it was appropriate to maintain a fact-based approach. Normally, in fact, the questions that make up the framework of ETAPAS indicators ask for the actual performance of an action, for example an indicator could ask the DTA owner: “Did your organization provide a feedback channel for feedback or queries to the final users of the DTA?”.

¹ See Figure 1

On the other hand, the starting point for the definition of the individual indicators were the risks of the **ETAPAS Risk framework**, to ensure coverage of all the identified risks. Following the literature, possible mitigation actions for each risk were also analysed and ranked, in order to allow assessment of the level of mitigation for each risk against which an action was implemented. As a result, we categorised the indicators depending on whether they assess the presence of the risk or the effectiveness of any mitigation action eventually put in place. The literature was also source of inspiration in the process of building the individual indicators, most of which maintain the “question-type” format as in the best practices identified. Where the indicators were taken from the literature, the framework also reports the source(s) in a dedicated column. Furthermore, each indicator has been mapped against both the principles, and therefore the relevant ethical issues, and the main risk category addressed².

To get to the current version, the ETAPAS indicators framework went through several rounds of **consultation**. In particular, we decided to have consultation with the use cases’ teams: each use case team is composed by the use case owner, the public sector organisation, and the technology provider. Having both at the meetings allowed to gather feedback from representatives of the public administrations and public sector organisations involved, which are the main target of the RDT Indicators Framework, as well as from technical experts from the technology providers who are central stakeholders for the ETAPAS tools.

In addition, we felt it necessary to have consultations with 2021.AI, the ETAPAS Consortium Partner responsible for the development of the prototypical software platform that will support the assessment.

These consultations were very useful in order to ensure that the platform could support the current structure of the framework and in order to identify further indicators, in particular those of a computational nature which are periodically and often automatically collected by the platform.

We have also periodically coordinated with the Lisbon Council, the Consortium Partner responsible for the stakeholder validation approach to be applied to the RDT Indicators Framework, to ensure that the methodology was aligned with the tools we were developing and thus provide an integrated approach.

More specifically, the following consultations were implemented:

- Individual meetings with each use case team and 2021.AI;
- Sharing material with each use case team and collecting feedback in writing;
- Individual meeting with 2021.AI;
- Individual meetings with the Lisbon Council³;
- Extended regular meetings with all participants in WP3 activities;
- Sharing material with each use case team and collecting feedback in writing;
- Sharing material with 2021.AI and collecting feedback in writing;
- Individual meeting with 2021.AI on computational indicators;
- Sharing material with the whole Consortium in order to gather feedback.

Figure 5 below shows the key dates of the consultation process that was followed to draft and refine the ETAPAS Indicators Framework.

² The risk categories are those of the ETAPAS Risk framework outlined in **Chapter 3**

³ The Lisbon Council is the Consortium Partner responsible for the stakeholder validation approach (SWIFT methodology) to be applied to the indicators framework

Figure 5: Timeline of the consultation process for the RDT Indicator Framework

The indicators framework, in its first version, was shared and discussed in individual meetings with each of the four use case teams to refine and validate it. These meetings were also attended by 2021.AI, the consortium partner that will develop the platform, and the Lisbon Council, which, through the methodology described in Deliverable 3.3 “Validation method and guidelines”, assisted the discussion to receive constructive feedback. Following the consultations with the use case teams, written feedback was requested from them and a further meeting with 2021.AI was held to collect comments.

Ad hoc discussion sessions regarding computational indicators have also been organised with 2021.AI. It is important to emphasize that some of the indicators have been devised from consultations, particularly those with use cases teams, which have also involved public administrations, and with 2021.AI, the provider of the platform that will be developed in ETAPAS. To give an example, the indicator “Did your organisation ensure compliance with the GDPR in developing and using the DTA?” has been proposed by the Ministry of the Economy and Finance and was integrated into the framework. In general, the process of creating the framework was participatory, and many features were tested through consultations, some of which were removed, while others were validated.

As mentioned, the last step of the consultation process, was the sharing of material with the whole Consortium in order to gather feedback. In particular, feedback was gathered through a questionnaire in the form of a Google Form, which can be consulted in **Annex 2**.

The resultant first version of the ETAPAS indicators framework will thus be used in the ETAPAS use cases during the piloting phase, **Chapter 7** of the document will detail the expected activities and results from each use case implementation. The lessons learned from the use cases will finally inform the development of an improved version of the framework, of a Governance Model and of an improved version of the platform by the end of the project.

3.3. Overall Indicator Framework structure

As outlined in **Section 3.1** about the Methodology applied for the Indicators Framework, the approach to building the framework was defined starting from the first ETAPAS research outcomes and the analysis of the literature and refined through several consultations with relevant partners in the consortium.

Below we list the 14 rationales that resulted from the process described, explaining for each of them the sources, logic and derivation criteria applied.

Rationale 1

The ETAPAS indicators framework includes two types of indicators: assessment indicators structured as a fact-based general checklist and that may be text, numeric, single choice, multiple choice, yes/no, ratio grid and direct feedback indicators; and computational indicators tailored to each specific use case/DTA.

The analysis of the best practices revealed the limitations of purely quantitative approaches to this type of assessment concerning especially social-ethical issues and showed the merits of a check-list approach. Most of the analysed framework⁴ were structured as a list of questions categorised according to specific criteria, such as the relevant ethical issue or the risk to be avoided or mitigated. Our approach has been to develop the **assessment indicators** from individual risks in order to ensure their coverage and to track the indicators towards both the main risk category and the relevant ethical principle to allow categorisation. We later determined that the most efficient categorisation criterion was risk categories, as they were more specific to the indicators than the ethical principles, whereas individual risk could not be applied as a criterion because indicators almost always measure more than one risk. Moreover, many of the frameworks analysed included many self-assessment questions, which are not very objective and generalisable. Given the stringent socio-ethical requirements of the public sector and the ambition to generalise the framework, we chose a fact-based approach. This type of approach consists of asking the person carrying out the assessment whether or not they have carried out an action, whether the technological solution used has certain characteristics, or something that is factual and does not require subjective judgement.

The questions constituting the **assessment indicators** can be of different types, they can for example have a list of answers to choose from or expect a numerical answer, on this issue, we have chosen to maintain the categorisation provided by the Grace platform by 2021.AI: **text, numeric, single choice, multiple choice, yes/no and ratio grid questions**. This categorisation covered all the indicators envisaged, with the exception of two types, the “direct feedback” and “computational” indicators, which for their special features we decided to maintain as stand-alone categories.

By “**direct feedback**” indicators we mean those types of assessment question that require direct answers from the final user, defined as “the person that is impacted by the decision taken by the DT, without directly interacting with it”. These are the only indicators that involve subjective self-assessment. A direct feedback indicator is for example: “How much does the user feel safe while interacting with the DTA? [Very safe, somehow safe, not totally safe, unsafe]”. These types of indicators are particularly useful to assess qualitative aspects of the final user experience with the DTA.

By “**computational**” indicators, on the other hand, we mean those metrics that can be used to derive automatically from a set of data an assessment score for a certain risk-aspect of the DTA. These indicators, due to their special automatic nature, need to be tailored to each specific use case and deserve a separate sheet of the framework. An example of a “computational” indicator for the use case concerning Robot-mediated rehabilitation is: “Event from navigation system recorded online on the platform to measure potential physical harm and collision with the patient/therapist”. This type of indicator allows certain aspects of the DTA to be continuously monitored, making it possible to monitor particularly risky areas in relation to the specific use case.

Rationale 2

The assessment indicators may be of two types: those assessing if the risk is relevant (risk indicators) and those that evaluate the effectiveness of the mitigation actions (mitigation indicators).

We noticed that the frameworks analysed in the literature presented two types of questions, although not explicitly categorised in this sense:

⁴ For the list of the analysed framework see Annex 1

- Risk questions: assessing whether the risk was present and relevant to the specific DTA or not;
- Mitigation questions: checking whether certain risk mitigation actions have been put in place.

As these indicators investigate different aspects of risk application, but may refer to the same risks, we considered it necessary to integrate both types of indicators into the ETAPAS framework.

Rationale 3

If the risk is present (i.e., the answer to the risk question indicates that the risk is present) then related mitigation indicators/questions are presented to the organisation and have to be answered. Some mitigation indicators, however, are of a mandatory nature and should be asked independently of the related risk indicator answer.

We considered risk and mitigation indicators to be consequential. In fact, only if the risk applies and is relevant to the specific DTA, actions to mitigate that risk should be implemented and thus mitigation indicators should be presented to the organisation undertaking the assessment through the platform dashboard. One of the reasons we chose this approach relies in the request of having a – as much as possible – light and modular tool received from the consulted PS organisations.

As exemplified by **Figure 6** below, following this approach, there should be a risk assessment dashboard, presenting the risk question to the user of the platform. On the base of the user input, the platform should redirect the user to the mitigation assessment dashboard if the risk applies to the case, or otherwise directly to the next risk question.

Figure 6: Risk and mitigation assessment dashboards example

However, once this type of approach was established, we realised that, since risk questions often embrace several specific risks, a negative answer could only partially exclude the application of some mitigation actions. Because of this, we categorised some mitigation indicators as “mandatory”. These indicators are always shown in the dashboard whatever the answer to the risk question. This feature allows the ETAPAS assessment to be more comprehensive, always covering crucial areas of risk. An example of a mitigation question that we deemed worthy of the “mandatory” label is: “Did your organization inform relevant stakeholders (users & final users) that the DT is used in your products and/or services? [Yes; No]”. Note that mandatory mitigation questions, while referring to actions to mitigate a specific risk, are more general in nature and apply to most cases.

Rationale 4

The mitigation indicators are organized based on risk indicators to which they refer (in other words, the leading risk indicator addresses the same risks that the related mitigation actions/indicators are intended to mitigate). This relationship is made evident by the ID of the mitigation indicators which always refer to the risk indicator number (for example if the risk indicator is identified by the code I.1, the mitigation indicators will be I.1.1, I.1.2 and so on).

Given the consequential nature of risk and mitigation indicators highlighted by **Rationale 3**, it was necessary to make clear which mitigation actions were related to each leading risk question. The a priori need for a coding system for the ETAPAS indicators, in line with best practices, was combined with this additional need. The resulting coding system is based on the numbering of the risk questions according to the order of their presentation to the user of the platform. Accordingly, the first risk indicator that will be shown in the dashboard will be “I.1”, which stands for “indicator number 1”. Mitigation indicators will be labelled starting from the related risk indicator, so that the first mitigation indicator shown for the risk indicator “I.1” will be “I.1.1”. Basically, mitigation indicators add a layer to the numbering format.

With regard to computational indicators, as these indicators are specific and tailored to each use case, they deserve a different coding system. In particular, the identification code begins with a “C”, standing for “Computational indicator”, and numbers follow according to the number of the use case and the internal order of the indicators. Accordingly, the first computational indicator shown for the 1st ETAPAS use case will be labelled “C1.1”.

Rationale 5

Indicators for assessing National/Overnational risks, which refer to risks related to the whole of a country or nation or over a nation, rather than to a single DTA or use case, will not be identified as the focus of the ETAPAS project is supporting PAs in implementing real DT-based use cases with a practical approach.

Some of the risks identified by the ETAPAS Risk Framework have been categorised as “National/Overnational” since they refer to global or national issues, not solvable, but possibly amplifiable, by the individual DTA, some examples of this kind of risks are social isolation, concentration of power, democratic deficit or loss of cultural diversity. Understandably, it may become prohibitively challenging to try to assess how much a single DT application in a public sector organisation may, for example, contribute to the risk of democratic deficit. As the objective of ETAPAS is to provide practical and useful tools for public organisations to reduce ethical, social and legal risks in adopting DTAs, no specific indicators have been constructed from this type of risks. However, some of their aspects are included in indicators that assess related risks.

Rationale 6

Indicators for assessing Organisational-level risk, on the other hand, are included in the framework, however since they depend on features of the PS organisation and not on those of the DTA, they have to be answered just once by each organisation undertaking the assessment.

Another outreach level for the risks, according to the ETAPAS Risk Framework, is the Organisational one, this category includes risks that arise directly from the organisation that is adopting the DTA, such as the “waste of resource” risk. Initially, we assumed that the indicators/questions assessing this kind of risks should be answered just once per each organisation undertaking the assessment, even if for different DTAs. This is because these risks stem directly from the type and structure of the organisation that is adopting the new technology application. An example of organisational level mitigation indicator is “Has your organisation adopted a set of ethical principles/code of conduct concerning the adoption of technologies and shared it with all employees? [Yes; No]”. However, as we moved forward in developing the indicators, we realized that some indicators that were organizational in nature, were useful to ask even multiple times during implementation or afterwards.

This is also because we expanded the "Organisational" category to include more indicators as a result of consultations with use case teams. An example of an organizational level indicator that should be shown and answered during and after DTA implementation is: "Does your organization have a plan of fault tolerance via e.g., a duplicated system or another parallel system (DT-based or "conventional")?".

Rationale 7

For each indicator there should be an indication of the related ethical principles and the leading one from the ETAPAS Code of Conduct, the latter representing the core ethical issue addressed.

The indicators of the ETAPAS framework assess the application of a risk, the effectiveness of possible mitigation measures, in order to be compliant with a number of ethical principles, such as environmental sustainability, justice, transparency or privacy. For completeness, we set out to create a multidimensional framework, where both the level of compliance with the principle and the level of risk guides the assessment and scoring. The prioritisation of the principles, that will be carried out by each use case team, will also have an effect on the indicators too, namely providing a sort of prioritisation of the indicators on which focussing when carrying out the assessment of the use case. Therefore, in order to keep track of which ethical issue is assessed by each indicator, the indicator framework shows both the related principles and the "leading ethical principle" from the ETAPAS Code of Conduct for each individual assessment or computational indicator.

Rationale 8

For each indicator there should be an indication of the risks which are intended to be assessed (usually more than one), as well as of the main risk category of reference from the ETAPAS Risk framework.

As already highlighted, the RDT indicators framework assesses the level of risk on the basis of the 35 risks identified by the ETAPAS Risk Framework. When identifying and constructing the indicators, we realised that very often, especially in the area of mitigation indicators, one action mitigated several risks, just as one risk indicator could assess the applicability and relevance of several risks simultaneously. These risks, however, very often belonged to the same of the 8 ETAPAS risk categories. Or, even in cases where this was not the case, there was a prevailing risk category, which we named: "leading risk category". Accordingly, the leading risk category is the main criterion that we have selected for the categorisation of the assessment indicators, and they will be presented on the basis of this criterion in **Chapter 4**. On the other hand, for computation indicators a detail description of the structure and content is to be found in **Chapter 5**, for the moment, it is sufficient to know that the main categorisation criterion in this case is the specific use case/DTA. With regard to the mapping of indicators against risks, all risks are covered because we started from risks in developing the indicators, while details on frequency can be explored in **Section 3.3**. It is important to underline that both the risk categories and the individual risks mapped by the framework play a key role in scoring.

Rationale 9

For each indicator there should be an indication of the relevant implementation stage for undertaking that specific assessment. In particular, the framework indicates whether an assessment indicator is to be assessed ex ante (before implementation), during implementation, or ex post (after implementation) and the time frame of the periodical detection for computational indicators

We looked at various possibilities with regard to the timing of the assessment, the safest and most comprehensive solution seemed to be to split the phases with respect to the implementation cycle of the technology application. Therefore, the RDT indicator framework indicates for each individual indicator whether its assessment should be completed, one or more times:

- Ex ante (before implementation);

- During implementation;
- Ex post (after implementation).

In the context of the ETAPAS use cases implementation, the relevant ethical, legal and social assessment will be performed four times, one time before, two times during and one time after implementation, so as to cover all the implementation stages and to guarantee ethical compliance within the entire cycle of the DTA. It is worth noting that the assessment configuration will differ each time the assessment will be performed depending on the implementation stage, since some risk and some mitigation indicators are required just in some of the implementation phases but not in the others.

Of course, in line with the suggestion from the ETAPAS Code of Conduct, principle 10, “continuous evaluation and improvement” is always needed. Accordingly, our suggestion is to evaluate on an hoc basis the required number of assessment iterations, especially during the implementation phase. As a base value four during the whole implementation cycle is a balanced estimate.

Also in this case, a different treatment is reserved to computational indicators. Many computational indicators, in fact, consist in the automatic or semi-automatic data or event detection by the platform directly from the DTA. Since detection is periodic, in the case of computational indicators the time frame of the periodical detection will be indicated instead of the relevant implementation stage to undertake the assessment. However, the standard timing section (ex-ante, during, ex post) will be showed in the case the computational indicator is not automatic.

Rationale 10

Given that the ETAPAS indicators framework should be general and relevant for the largest possible number of DTs, each assessment indicator should be applicable to the context of the largest possible number of DTs, while for each computational indicator it will be explicitly stated to which list of DTs it can be applied. The possibilities foreseen in this respect by the current version of the RDT Indicator Framework are: Cross/Generic (i.e., applicable to all DTs), Big Data/Open Data, AI, Robotics, Blockchain, IoT, VR/AR.

It is not an easy task to identify common characteristics among DTs that would make it possible to create an assessment generic enough to cover them all. In our research work, we realised that some of the features that characterise specific technologies are precisely those from which major ethical or social impacts can arise. For this reason, we have tried, while maintaining the intention of developing a generic assessment for all DTs, to include more specific indicators, which perhaps apply only to some DTs. This second intention is complemented by the computational indicators that are much more tailored to the specific use case/DTA. In the first version of the framework also for assessment indicators there was a specific dimension named "Relevant DTs" which presented the following options:

- Cross/Generic;
- Big Data/Open Data;
- AI;
- Robotics;
- Blockchain;
- IoT;
- VR/AR.

However, in the work of developing and refining the indicators, also by combining different sources from the literature, we were able to generalise the assessment indicators and realised that this dimension of the framework was more relevant to the computational indicators. It is worth noticing

that the list of DTs presented above includes technologies from the ETAPAS use cases (AI, Robotics and Big Data), but also technologies that are spreading more rapidly within the public sector and have more controversial ethical impacts. The ETAPAS use cases have been selected precisely with the intention of covering disruptive technologies with these characteristics and having different levels of maturity, so as to co-design the tools with stakeholders representing the majority of foreseeable cases. The same list of DTs remains available in the context of computational indicators, also with a view to giving an indication for their applicability to different use cases.

Rationale 11

Since the ETAPAS indicator framework aims to assess the ethical, social and legal risks faced by a public organization in adopting a DTs, it must specify which of the stakeholders involved in this process should be responsible for or otherwise involved in the assessment of each specific indicator.

The risks identified by the ETAPAS Risk Framework, as well as the assessment indicators, relate to several different aspects of the DTA adoption process, for example they embrace both governance and technology aspects, as well as legal or social aspects, humane-machine interaction and much more. Consequently, the responsibility for risk mitigation as well as ethical or legal compliance may be in the hands of different stakeholders depending on the stage of implementation and the scope of the assessment indicators. In this regard, we have included the dimension "Relevant stakeholders" in the framework to indicate who in practice has responsibility or is key to address that indicator. The generic categories of stakeholders that we have derived, taking inspiration from the literature but also through the feedback collected during the consultations with public sector organisations, are the following:

- Final user - the person that is impacted by the decision taken by the DTA;
- User - the person that makes decision based on the DTA;
- Developer – the professional that develops the computer software for the DTA;
- DTA Owner (Use Case Owner) - the organisation that owns the DTA;
- PA organisation's Management – the responsible Management team from the PA organisation that is adopting the DTA.

The distinction between User and Final Users deserves special attention, a concrete example may help to understand the difference. Take the ETAPAS Use case "Robot-mediated rehabilitation", dealing with a humanoid robot used for the assessment of patients' walking abilities, there the final user is the patient, while the doctor, who takes the decision based on the DTA outcomes, is the user. In practical terms, we intended the indication of this dimension of the framework to be used by the platform user to collect information from relevant stakeholders when completing the assessment. It is important to note, that depending on the use cases/DTA, some stakeholder categories might coincide. In addition, often more than one stakeholder category may be relevant to an assessment indicator, in which case the framework reports both. Computational indicators do not need this indication, as they are mainly automated.

Rationale 12

Both when the source of the indicator is a best practice from the literature and when the indicator is a result of ETAPAS research, the source of the assessment indicator is explicitly stated.

Since, as already mentioned, some of the assessment indicators were taken from best practices in the literature, we thought it appropriate to keep the source indication in a specific dimension of the framework. Therefore, the RDT Indicators Framework reports either:

- The source from the literature with the link to the downloadable version of the document or the website where the source is available;

- The wording "ETAPAS consortium", which indicate that the indicator was developed by the team of authors of this deliverable or was the result of internal consultations within the ETAPAS consortium, as described in **Section 3.1 Methodology applied for the Indicator Framework**.

An example of an "ETAPAS Consortium" indicator is: "What metrics did you use in order to validate that the number of inaccurate predictions was acceptable?", which was proposed by the SINTEF/PROKOM use case team in the context of the consultations.

On the other hand, as far as computational indicators are concerned, this indication is not necessary because they were all developed by the ETAPAS Consortium, and in particular by the authors of this deliverable in collaboration with 2021.AI and the use case teams.

Rationale 13

To enable public sector organizations to easily carry out the assessment, guidelines will be provided for each indicator, including considerations on how to interpret and assess the indicator and how to relate it to the specific context of application, as well as providing explanations on the possible answers.

As the name of this deliverable might suggest, from the conception of the project idea, ETAPAS aims to develop, together with the RDT Indicators Framework, "Measurement Guidelines" to make the assessment accessible and user-friendly. These guidelines are specific to each indicator and represent a further dimension of the framework. They contain all the information needed by the user of the platform to correctly interpret the indicator, by way of example they normally include:

- aim of the indicator;
- explanations delimiting the context of applicability;
- explanations on how to answer the question or answer to the indicator.

The feature of being user-friendly is central to ETAPAS' objective of providing practical and easy-to-use tools that are accessible to all public sector organisations that may need them. Much emphasis has also been placed on this aspect in consultations with stakeholders and especially public sector organisations.

Rationale 14

In addition to indirectly suggesting mitigation actions through the mitigation indicators, the RDT Indicator Framework explicitly suggests for each indicator some "recommendations/best practices" that might be followed in order to improve the assessment score in that particular risk area.

Leveraging the extensive research work carried out within ETAPAS to develop the whole RDT framework, we have selected best practices from the literature and identified the most effective mitigation actions for the specific risks assessed by each indicator so as to report them in the framework.

Based on the feedback received by the consortium partners also in the previous phase of the project related to the importance of practical and easy-to-use guidelines on how to avoid risks and respect the defined principles, we deemed fundamental to integrate these best practices and recommendations for each indicator. We think that this information can be important for the public sector organisation that is carrying out the assessment also in the light of the fact that the "recommendations/best practices" can be used for improving the score of the assessment in the case it results low in certain risk areas.

RDT Indicator Framework Structure

Given these rationales, we derived a comprehensive framework in the form of an excel file composed by:

- A **Frontpage** sheet, containing general information about the deliverable, the authors and reviewers list;
- A **Principles** sheet, listing the 10 principles from the ETAPAS Code of Conduct, together with their ID (e.g., P1, P2 and so on) and description;
- A **Risk Framework** sheet, containing the whole ETAPAS Risk framework (8 risk categories, 35 risks);
- An **Assessment indicators** sheet, containing the ETAPAS risk and mitigation indicators;
- A **Computational indicators** sheet, including the proposed computational indicator for the four ETAPAS use cases;
- An **Acronyms and Definition** sheet, listing useful acronyms and definition to properly interpret the framework.

As can be noted, the structure of the RDT indicator framework reflects the interconnections between the various elements of the whole ETAPAS RDT framework (see the **Principles** and the **Risk Framework** sheets).

Still, the core part of the RDT Indicator framework is represented by the **Assessment Indicators** and the **Computational indicators** sheets, since they contain all the indicators for the assessment of the social, ethical and legal compliance of DT applications in the Public Sector developed by ETAPAS.

In particular, the current structure of the ETAPAS **Assessment Indicators** sheet is as follows:

ID	Identification code
Risk indicator	The question or measure or index that assess a risk aspect
Mitigation indicator	The question or measure or index that assess the mitigation actions
Type of indicator	Indicate the type of indicator in terms on how to compile it, such as: Text, Numeric, Single choice, Multiple choice, Yes/No, Ratio Grid questions, Direct feedback
Related risks	Relevant risks that the indicator is assessing/measuring
Leading risk category	The leading risk category addressed by the indicator
Related principles	Relevant ethical issues addressed by the indicator
Leading principle	The central ethical issue addressed by the indicator
Guidelines	Question explanation (specific examples, definitions) and explanation of each possible answer
Recommendations	Explanation of the best practices that should be followed for each indicator
Timing	How many times and at what stage of the use case development the indicator should be calculated
Mandatory	Whether a mitigation indicator should be asked independently of the related risk indicator answer
Relevant Stakeholders	Record of the type of stakeholder that should be engaged to measure the indicator such as: Final User, User, Developer, DTA owner, PA organisation's Management
Source	Source of the indicator

The sheet reports the above information for each assessment indicator in the framework. As mentioned, assessment indicators are of two types: risk and mitigation; by way of example the tables below show the information provided by the framework for a risk indicator and a related mitigation indicator in the governance risk category.

ID	I.2
Risk indicator	Has your organization defined a clear purpose in using the identified DT application (e.g. operational efficiency and cost reduction)?
Type of indicator	Yes/No question
Possible answers	Yes; No
Related risks	Use for unintended purposes (3.1); Lack of transparency and explainability (3.2); Waste of resources (3.6); Unclear accountability and responsibilities (3.7)
Related principle	P4. Responsibility and accountability; P10. Continuous evaluation and improvement; P3. Transparency & Explainability as related principles
Guidelines	This risk indicator is related to the governance risks and more specifically the objective of the use of a particular DTA in a specific situation/ (use) case. The use of DTAs should not be the be-all and end-all. Generally, DTAs should be chosen as part of the solution when they offer some added value that cannot be achieved through conventional approaches. Thus, the objective of employing a specific DTA in a specific case, as well as, if possible, the expected contribution/improvement /enhancement, should be clearly and explicitly defined. Additionally, the operational efficiency of the DTA, and the impact it might have on costs (reduced costs) should be documented and described.
Recommendations	The organization should define and document the DTA's purpose and context of the application.
Timing	Once, ex-ante (Before the implementation)
Relevant Stakeholders	DTA Owner (Use Case Owner); PA organisation's Management
Source	The World Economic Forum (January 2020) "Companion to the Model AI Governance Framework – Implementation and Self-Assessment Guide for Organizations" https://www.pdpc.gov.sg/-/media/Files/PDPC/PDF-Files/Resource-for-Organisation/AI/SGLsago.pdf

ID	I.2.1
Mitigation indicator	Did your organization consider whether the decision to use the DT for a specific application/use case is consistent with its core values and/or societal expectations?
Type of indicator	Yes/No question
Possible answers	Yes; No
Mandatory	Yes
Related risks	Autonomous weapons proliferation (5.2), Malicious surveillance (5.3), Disinformation (5.4), Democratic deficit (5.5), Citizen scoring (5.6)
Related principle	P4. Responsibility and accountability; P5. Safety and security; P6. Privacy
Guidelines	The aim of this mitigation indicator is to identify whether the organization has considered the consistency of adopting this specific DTA with the ethical principles they want to stand for and be associated with.
Recommendations	<p>(If the answer to this question is negative) consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing a set of ethical principles that are in line with or can be incorporated into the organization’s mission statement. • In the use case definition, evaluate if the objective for which the DTA was created can be aligned with the defined principles. • Outline how to adopt (e.g., contextualize) the DTA in practice while being consistent with the principles. <p>A best practice that should be followed in any case, is the development of a Code of Ethics for the use of the DTA. Relevant areas to should be considered include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulatory risks (e.g., compliance with Singapore's Personal Data Protection Act 2012 (PDPA) and sectoral regulations) • Public relations risks (e.g., public perception towards the organization's AI practices) • Costs (e.g., impact of incorporating governance practices into the organization’s current legacy business models and organizational structure)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Resources and internal champions to drive responsible adoption/implementation of the DTA
Timing	Once, ex-ante (Before the implementation)
Relevant Stakeholders	PA organisation's Management
Source	The World Economic Forum (January 2020) "Companion to the Model AI Governance Framework – Implementation and Self-Assessment Guide for Organizations" https://www.pdpc.gov.sg/-/media/Files/PDPC/PDF-Files/Resource-for-Organisation/AI/SGIsago.pdf

Chapter 4 will provide details about the content of the Assessment Indicators sheet.

On the other hand, the current structure of the ETAPAS **Computational Indicators** sheet is as follows:

ID	Identification code
Use Case	Use case for which the indicator was developed
Indicator	The computational indicator that monitors the technology in a quantitative way, assesses a risk aspect or mitigation actions
Description	Description of the computational indicator and how it can be measured
Timing	If the indicator is periodically detected it shows the time frame of the periodical detection, otherwise it shows whether the assessment should be undertaken ex ante, during or after implementation
Related risks	Relevant risks that the indicator is assessing/measuring
Leading risk category	The leading risk category addressed by the indicator
Related principles	Relevant ethical issues addressed by the indicator
Leading principle	The central ethical issue addressed by the indicator
Relevant DTs for replication	DTs to which the indicator can be eventually applied

By way of example the table below show the information provided by the framework for a computational indicator designed for the ETAPAS Use Case 4 “Public Organizations Multi-factor Misinformation Handling”.

ID	C4.2
Indicator	Is it about immigrants or violence - racial slur tracker
Description	The Racial slur scanner aims at giving quick insights about racial slur in a given directory or database. It searches a selected datasource for different preselected "themes" and then if found, report the location and frequency
Timing	Periodically detected – timeframe TBD
Related risks	Biased outcomes (4.2); Unequal access and benefit (4.3); Loss of cultural diversity (4.4)
Leading risk category	Enhancing inequality and discrimination
Related principles	P2. Justice, equality and the rule of law / P10. Continuous evaluation and improvement
Leading principle	P2. Justice, equality and the rule of law
Relevant DTs for replication	AI, Robotics, Big Data

Chapter 5 provides a description of the current version of the Computational Indicators sheet.

3.4. Key insights from the RDT Indicator Framework

This section presents the key insights extracted from the analysis of the risk and mitigation indicators along with the principles presented in the RDT framework. Each of the identified indicators, both assessment and computational, is associated with a leading risk category and a leading principle, as well as the related risks and principles. By using diagrams and heatmaps, the indicators included

within the RDT framework have been analysed and presented in a user-friendly way. This analysis allows the identification of probable overlapping between risk indicators, or lack of either risk or mitigation indicators in a risk category or principle. An overview of the distribution of indicators among the different risk categories and principles and a presentation of the relationship between the risks associated with the indicators can offer valuable insight about the extent of the RDT framework’s focus on the different risk categories and ethical principles. Additionally, this analysis highlights the most prevalent aspects of the framework and can be used as a confirmation of a meaningful approach.

Percentage (%) of risk indicators per risk category

Percentage (%) of mitigation indicators per risk category

Figure 7: Pie charts presenting the percentage of both risk and mitigation indicators per risk category

The above pie charts (Figure 7) demonstrate the distribution of the leading risks associated with the assessment indicators, (a) for risk indicators and (b) for mitigation indicators. Although the two charts are rather similar, the two distributions are not identical. These differences are primarily a result of the fact that the number of mitigation indicators corresponding to each risk indicators is not fixed. The prevalent leading risk, for both charts, is “Security and data protection risks” category, showcasing the importance of data safety, closely followed by “Errors and misuse”, indicating a high focus on potential mismanagement and corruption, and including risks related to the misuse of the DT, which are of fundamental importance in the PS. More information on this category is available in section 4.5.

Percentage (%) of risk indicators per principle

Percentage (%) of mitigation indicators per principle

Figure 8: Pie charts presenting the percentage of both risk and mitigation indicators per principle

The above pie charts (Figure 8) demonstrate the distribution of the leading principles associated with the assessment indicators, (a) for risk indicators and (b) for mitigation indicators. Although the two charts are rather similar, the two distributions are not identical. The prevalent leading principle for

both charts is P5 referring to safety and security principle. The increased percentage in both risk indicators and mitigation indicators in this principle indicates the importance given to the control of the security of the systems to be controlled, as well as the observance of the necessary procedures for the DT to be compliant with all regulations.

The second most addressed principle, in both risk and mitigation indicators, is P2 that is the principle related with the justice, equality and the rule of law. This principle refers to the introduction of technologies that promote equality of access and opportunity should be strongly prioritized. But technologies can also, inadvertently, have the opposite effect. For instance, algorithms can become biased against minorities or against women if they are trained on data that reflects previous bias and discrimination. This principle is one of the leading principles for the ETAPAS project and according to the fifth rationale presented in section 3.3, the ETAPAS framework aims to provide practical tools that will reduce ethical social and legal risks, by minimizing biases, eliminating discrimination and inequality and help in the implementation of DTs that are compliant with the law of and all the corresponding regulations. Additionally, the mitigation indicators related to this principle are more than those to the other principles, since the scope of most of the mitigation actions include the concept of justice and the development of trust between the DT and the organisation. At this point it should be mentioned that many mitigation actions can be put in place via process steps but also via computational indicators (e.g., there are many fairness measurement indices available on the research field and bias mitigation is one of the most active research areas also in terms of technical solutions).

On the same note, it is also worth mentioning that the principle with the lowest percentage is the P8 “Retaining human contacts” which is the leading principle for 1% of the mitigation indicators and for none of the risk indicators. This principle may be present in only the 1% of the mitigation indicators as a leading principle, however it is mentioned in more risk and mitigation indicators as a related principle. The difference of this is the scope of this principle that is in a close relationship with P3 – “Transparency and explainability” and P4 – “Responsibility and accountability”, which are both focusing on the transparency and explainability of the DTs outcome to its final users and the public, along with the responsibility of the decision maker to be accountable to the citizens for the activities of public authorities and other entities under their direction. Through both principles, it is clear that the goal is to improve relations with citizens, to improve communication and transparency in procedures, but also to try to improve the decision-making that concerns them in a public body.

Apart from the aforementioned pie charts, a heatmap (Figure 3) has been created including the correlations of the related risks. The aim of this heatmap is to help us understand any connections/correlations existing between different risks. It is of great importance to analyse the relations that different risks have between them, find any correlation or even detect any overlays on the scope of the existing risk categories. The values included in this heatmap depict how many times two related risks were presented in the risk and mitigation indicators.

Figure 9: Assessment Indicators Related Risks Heatmap

The heatmap of the related risks (Figure 9) that are associated with each assessment indicator (both risk and mitigation) presents the co-occurrence between pairs of risks, while its diagonal presents the total number of assessment indicators that are associated with the specific risk. High values depicted within the heatmap, e.g., the value 14 that corresponds to the pair [Exclusion of individuals (1.3), Unequal access and benefit (4.3)] confirm the close relation between the two related risks. This relation is expected, since the scope of the 1.3 risk and the 4.3 risk are closely related.

Another interesting correlation is the one between the risk 4.2 – “Biased outcomes” and 6.1 – “Rogue applications” and also the 6.2 – “Hacking to change the behaviour of the DT” risk with the 4.2 – “Biased outcomes”. These risks are related as through the biased outcome discriminations might increase and therefore the DTA might be used for purposes it was not designed to serve. Additionally, the biased outcome might be resulted from a hacked dataset or wrong information provided as input within the DT, which might result also from an adversarial attach. Thus, 6.2 and 4.2 risks are related since 4.2 might be a result of a hacking risk mentioned in 6.2.

On the other hand, the lack of high values in the heatmap indicates that the degree of overlapping between the risks is not high, leading to the conclusion that the contribution of all risks is valuable and that the risk framework is solid.

A mapping of principles against risk categories, as well as mappings of risk indicators and mitigation indicators against the corresponding related risks were also constructed and are available in “**Annex 2: RDT Indicator Framework Charts**”. The following pie chart (Figure 10) demonstrates the distribution of the risk categories associated with the computational indicators of the RDT Indicator Framework.

Figure 10: The percentages of the computational indicators defined per risk category

In the case of computational indicators, the most populated leading risk category are “Errors and misuse” and “Enhancing Inequality and discrimination”. On the other hand, no computational indicators are associated with the Work place issues leading risk category. In fact, according to the information retrieved for each use case all computational indicators seem to be oriented more on the computation of risks associated with the errors that might be caused from the DT either from a biased outcome or from a misuse of the DTA, rather than the issues referring to the work place. This is because the first type of risks can be calculated in a more effective manner through the use of computational indicators, than the work place issues. However, risks related with work place issues have a high percentage in the assessment indicators, and can be easily covered through the questions included within these indicators.

The next pie chart (Figure 11) demonstrates the distribution of the principles associated with the computational indicators.

Figure 11: The percentages of the computational indicators defined per principle

The most frequent leading principle in the case of computational indicators is P10 – “Continuous evaluation and performance”. This principle is related with the continuous evaluation that the DTA should have in order to be compliant with all laws and regulations, mitigate all risks and become sustainable. The information of added value retrieved from this pie chart is that no computational indicators have been associated with the principles P3 – “Transparency and accountability”, P7 – “Building an ethical culture involving employees”, P8 – “Retaining human contacts” and P9 – “Ethical public –private cooperation”. Most of the aforementioned principles have been covered from the assessment indicators (as presented in Figure 2), and therefore there was not given additional weight for them on the computational indicators. However, at this point it should be mentioned that the computational indicators are a work in progress, and will be further analysed in the other WPs, aiming to identify the sub-indicators per risk and principle, and also make any refinements on the related risks and principles for each indicator. **Chapter 4** below will provide an overview description of the assessment indicators.

4. Overview of the Assessment Indicators

This chapter provides an overview description of the assessment indicators included in the RDT Indicator Framework. As presented in the previous chapters, the assessment indicators are framed within eight risk categories:

- Risks concerning direct interaction with humans;
- Legal risks;
- Governance Risks;
- Enhancing inequality and discrimination;
- Errors and misuse;
- Security and data protection risks;
- Unsustainable use;
- Work place issues.

Each of these categories includes several risks, and for each of these risks several risk indicators related with the description of the risk have been defined. Likewise, for each risk indicator one or more mitigation indicators, associated with the corresponding risk indicator, have also been developed. It should be mentioned that, in line with the outlined approach, both risk and mitigation indicators of the assessment indicators are presented as questions, allowing in this way the corresponding stakeholders to better understand the content of each risk and be able to respond with greater confidence.

Aiming to create a more concrete framework, allowing users to easily access and use it for the evaluation of the adoption of DTs, a glossary has been designed, including the definitions of terms included in both the assessment and computational indicators. For each term its acronym, name, definition, and source have been listed. The idea behind the creation and analysis of the glossary lies in the need to present the terms and definitions contained within the RDT framework so that the different stakeholders filling the Assessment Indicators can first understand the rationale behind each definition and then answer each risk or mitigation question accordingly. Furthermore, it is also important to understand the definitions given for applying the recommendations provided for each mitigation or risk indicator. Thus, the glossary includes both general terms (e.g., Artificial Intelligence), along with more specific terms that are related with the RDT. The user is prompted to search for all the terms in the glossary if needed.

The categorization of the collected indicators and their assignment to the corresponding section within this deliverable has been made according to the risk indicators' leading risk category. The idea behind this assumption lies on the fact that the risk indicator is highly related with a certain risk category, while the mitigation indicators suggest some actions meant for mitigating the risk assessed by the risk indicator to which they are tied.

The following sections provide an overview description of the assessment objective of the developed indicators for each ETAPAS risk category, while a detailed description of all developed assessment indicators and related guidelines is to be found in Chapter 4 of Deliverable D3.2 "Measurement guidelines".

Risk concerning direct interaction with humans

The risk and mitigation indicators pertaining to this risk category aim to assess specific disruptive technologies applications which can be used for either reduce social networks, necessary for the cohesion of our communities, or introduce alternative human-based modes of contacts. This risk category includes 6 risks as follows: (1) replacement of human agency, (2) undisclosed technology use, (3) exclusion of individuals, (4) social isolation, (5) psychological harm, and (6) physical harm. Accordingly, this section of the assessment is meant to understand how the DTA interacts with the decision-making process of humans and assess whether it may cause damage, physical or psychological harms or affect through other negative impacts the involved stakeholders and their social relations.

Legal risks

The legal risk and mitigation indicators consider whether a specific disruptive technology application follows the fundamental rule of law, which public administration should never forget. These indicators make reference to 3 risks as follows: (1) illegal behaviour, (2) liability risks and (3) lack of certification procedures. Consequently, this part of the assessment investigates whether the organisation implementing the DTA has followed the rule of law in terms of procedures and adoption of relevant standards, as well as with respect to the treatment of personal data and the management of liability issues.

Governance risks

The governance risk and mitigation indicators are related to assessing whether the adoption of the disruptive technology is compliant with all the processes of interaction be they through the laws, norms, purposes or resources of the public sector organization. This risk category includes 7 risks as follows: (1) use for unintended purposes, (2) lack of transparency and explainability, (3) poor human oversight, (4) distrust, Relations with the private sector, (5) waste of resources, (6) unclear accountability and responsibilities. The indicators aim at ensuring that the organisation has a sound and clear governance structure to oversee the organization's use of the DTA, that relevant standard procedures are in place and that the DTA implementation meets both its intended purposes and societal expectations.

Enhanced inequality and discrimination

The risk and mitigation indicators of this risk category assess whether the application of the disruptive technology endure the basic principle of equal treatment, promoting equality of access. The indicators refer to 4 risks as follows: (1) concentration of power, (2) biased outcomes, (3) unequal access and benefit, (4) loss of cultural diversity. In particular, this section of the framework aims to ensure fairness in the DTA implementation, so that it does not exclude citizens from essential services nor discriminate against any minoritarian social group either directly or indirectly.

Errors and misuse

The risk and mitigation indicators of this risk category assess the disruptive technology application for the public sector in terms of potential unreliable outcomes, which can be of great damage for citizens. This risk category includes 6 risks as follows: (1) unreliable or poor-quality outcomes, (2) autonomous weapons proliferation, (3) malicious surveillance, (4) disinformation, (5) democratic deficit, and (6) citizen scoring. This section of the assessment embraces a complex range of issues which can lead to errors in and misuse of the DTA, ranging from risk stemming from the use of third-party datasets, to risks more specific to the public sector such as massive surveillance and citizen scoring.

Security and data protection risks

Security and data protection indicators assess whether the public sector organisation considers security regulation, and efficient measures to prevent and discover unauthorized use of data. This risk category includes 4 risks as follows: (1) rogue applications, (2) hacking to change the behaviour of the DT, (3) hacking to get information access, (4) loss of service continuity. The main focus of this part of the assessment is to ensure that the DTA is sufficiently safe from cybersecurity threats.

Unsustainable use

Unsustainable use indicators assess any natural or human-induced factor that directly or indirectly causes unsustainable use of natural resources. The indicators refer to 2 risks as follows: (1) high level of energy consumption, and (2) use of environmentally unsustainable materials. The main objective of this part of the assessment is to ensure that the DTA is developed and implemented in an environmentally sustainable manner.

Workplace issues

Workplace issues indicators assess job-related issues which can be caused by the new adoption of a specific disruptive technology within the public sector. These indicators refer to 2 risks as follows: (1) job displacement and (2) lack of competences. In particular, this part of the evaluation investigates whether staff involved in the various governance processes of the DTA are adequately trained and whether the DTA has a potential negative impact on the labour market.

5. Overview of the Computational Indicators

The necessity, or at least the usefulness, of including in the framework computational indicators became apparent from the very beginning of our research. With computational indicators we mean metrics that can be used to derive automatically from a set of data an assessment score for a certain risk-aspect of the DTA. As a matter of fact, where risk aspects can be investigated quantitatively or by ascertaining the occurrence of certain events, the AI-based platform that will be developed based on the Grace platform by 2021.AI can provide more efficiency in managing the assessment autonomously by connecting to the DTA. However, indicators working in this way can vary greatly on the basis of the technology on which the DTA is based. For example, the “PII (personally identifiable information) scanner” will be more useful for a Big Open Data platform, while an “Event from navigation system scanner” will only be useful for robotics applications that move within an environment. In addition, consultations with the use case teams revealed a desire for greater customisation of the indicators and the way in which they were measured, which was widely integrated in the development of computational indicators.

As mentioned, computational indicators were not taken from best practices, but exclusively co-designed with 2021.AI and the public administrations and technologic providers from the ETAPAS use cases. This has allowed us to ensure feasibility of their implementation, to have a much higher level of tailoring of the indicators since this first version, and to start a co-design process that will continue also in the following project phase. In particular, the **Test and Validation Phase** will be crucial for:

- Refining the list of proposed indicators and make them fully understandable by all the stakeholders of each use case;
- Defining limits and thresholds such as data requirements and connectors to actually collect these indicators;
- Identifying possible additional computational indicators to assess missing fundamental aspects and unforeseen risks.

The following sections provide an overview description of the developed indicators for each ETAPAS use case, while a detailed description of all developed computational indicators and related guidelines is to be found in Chapter 5 of Deliverable D3.2 “Measurement guidelines”.

UC1 – Ethically Responsible Big Open Data (MEF & CEA)

The first ETAPAS use case, named “Ethically Responsible Big Open Data” aims at identifying ethical issues, risks and impacts related to the open distribution of datasets via the NoiPA platform, a system created by the Department of General Administration of Personnel and Services (DAG) of Italian Ministry of Economy and Finance (MEF) with the goal of delivering efficient and innovative services to around 100 Italian central and local Public Bodies for the management of their personnel. In particular, the NoiPA platform offers legal and salary services, human capital management systems, as well as additional services. Since we are dealing with open anonymised datasets but also with information on public administration employees, it is clear that the risk of privacy breaches is quite central to this use case.

The use case team is composed by CEA, the technological provider, and the MEF, the PA use case owner. To deepen the context of the use case and jointly develop the most relevant indicators, we had several consultations (via videoconference and in writing) with the use case team and 2021.AI, to make sure that the use case owner would be able to validate its anonymisation procedures, ensure data fairness within datasets and have a transparent publication mechanism.

Following the consultations, we developed **6 indicators** for UC1 and in particular:

- 2 computational indicators addressing mainly **Privacy** issues, through testing for differential privacy on datasets and scanning of PII (personally identifiable information);
- 2 indicators dealing mainly with **Justice, equality and the rule of law**, and particularly regulatory compliance and bias management;
- 1 indicator addressing the **Responsibility and accountability** issue and dealing more specifically with the data governance;
- 1 indicator for **Continuous evaluation and improvement** enabled by statistics generator.

We also assessed the applicability of these tailored indicators within other DTA/use cases. For this reason, we have tried to maintain a fairly high level of generality at this early stage of computational indicators development. In general, the indicators developed and proposed for the MEF/CEA use case can be easily applied to other use cases/DTAs, especially if they are based on Big/Open Data or AI technologies, or if they involve datasets that may raise privacy, transparency or accountability concerns.

UC2 – Robot-mediated rehabilitation (IIT & FDG)

The second ETAPAS use case “Robot-mediated rehabilitation” is owned by Fondazione Don Carlo Gnocchi Onlus (FDG), a no-profit rehabilitation, assistance and clinical research centre accredited by the Italian National Health Service, and Italian Institute of Technology (IIT), a scientific research center established by the Italian Ministry of Education, University and Research and Ministry of Economy and Finance, in order to promote excellence in both basic and applied research and to facilitate the economic development at national level.

The use case focuses on the implementation of the R1 robot as an evaluator that will assess the performance of patients during rehabilitative tasks aimed to improve their balance and walking abilities. In particular the R1 robot is designed to replace the therapist as part of the Timed Up and Go (TUG) test. In the classical TUG test, the therapist measures the time taken by the patient to perform the task to assess the progress achieved throughout the rehabilitation. The R1 robot then becomes an intermediary between the patient and the therapist, who will interpret the feedback. As can be easily understood, this use case implies a wide variety of risks that derive both from its belonging to the medical field, and from the specific technology applied that involves a high degree of interaction with humans and the environment. Also in this case, numerous consultations have been carried out in order to catch all the significant aspects of the context of the use case, as well as the technical aspects that could be useful to derive computational indicators for this and similar DTAs.

Following the consultations, we developed **6 indicators** for UC2 and in particular:

- 4 computational indicators to enable **Continuous evaluation and improvement** and collecting in particular data on KPI on usage and datasets versioning, as well as events from speech and skeleton detection systems;
- 1 indicator addressing the **Safety and security** issue and dealing more specifically with the physical harm risk by collecting event from the R1 navigation system;
- 1 indicator assessing **Environmental sustainability**, by measuring energy consumption.

Generally speaking, the indicators developed and proposed for the IIT/FDG use case are more specific than those developed for use case 1, this partly stems from the fact that this use case is more mature, but also from the characteristics of the DTA that gives rise to specific ethical and social risks. In particular, the application in the medical field, as well as the continuous interaction of the robot with a patient, generate a considerable level of risk in the context of direct interaction with humans, such as physical or psychological harms, as well as in terms of accountability and responsibility. On the contrary, the energy consumption indicator can be applied to other use cases/DTA, as far as they involve energy consumption, as is usually the case. As a result, this indicator is widely applicable to allow for energy consumption monitoring and limit the risk of unsustainable processes and outcomes.

UC3 – The municipality chatbot Kommune-Kari (SINTEF & PROKOM)

The third ETAPAS use case deals with the chatbot “Kari” which supports more than 80 municipalities in Norway in providing municipality services to citizens. In particular, Kari is an AI-based virtual agent which directly interacts with the municipalities’ citizens by answering their questions of relevance, such as general information on the municipality services. Thanks to the chatbot, the municipalities manage to enhance citizens’ support service, as well as free public servants from routine tasks allowing them to focus on more value-added ones and preventing job losses. However, even within this use case there are ethical and social implications that come with the adoption of the DTA and are not to be underestimated, but assessed and managed. By way of example, particular risky areas may be identified in human agency and oversight, internal chatbot biases or equal access to information for everyone.

UC3 is owned by SINTEF, the Scandinavia's largest independent research organization and PROKOM, one of the main suppliers of digital solutions for the Norwegian public sector and creator of the “Kommune-Kari” chatbot. Although the use case team composition hasn't allowed us - for the moment - to get direct feedback from municipalities, the idea of sending direct questionnaires to public servants working for municipalities where Kari is used is being considered. In addition, consultations with this use case team were more focused on technical aspects and resulted in the development of the following proposed computational indicators.

Following the consultations, we developed **4 indicators** for UC3 and in particular:

- 2 computational indicators to enable **Continuous evaluation and improvement** and collecting in particular data on KPI on usage and events from the speech system;
- 2 indicators addressing **Justice, equality and the rule of law** and consisting of a racial slur scanner and an identifier of unexpected/novel requests.

As this use case also has a fairly high level of maturity, experience with the Kari chatbot across municipalities in Norway has already suggested that dialogue data can be valuable in understanding the possible ethical implications of a municipal chatbot. For example, users have been found to send questions to Kari about personal problems such as potential self-harm, loneliness, depression, anxiety, and even suicide. On this respect, there is a need to further investigate how to use these data, since they may represent an opportunity to lower the threshold for accessing health and social services, but may also be suggestive of an underlying, unaddressed need in the population.

UC4 - Public Organisations Multi-factor Misinformation Handling (CERTH & MUKA)

“Public Organisations Multi-factor Misinformation Handling” represents the fourth ETAPAS use case and is owned by the Centre for Research and Technology Hellas - Information Technologies Institute (CERTH-ITI) and the municipality of Katerini (MUKA), in Greece. The use case aims at assessing the use of AI for misinformation detection and prioritization of emerging issues in the Municipality of Katerini. While most of the municipalities are now equipped with online communication infrastructure, such as social media channels or information portals, it is clear that massive amounts of incoming information can nowadays only be collected and processed in automatic ways using Big Data and AI technologies. The same technologies can limit misinformation spreading, for example through news and social media merger summarization, topics clustering, classification and prioritization, graph-based fake news detector, public opinion (e.g., sentiment) analyser and visual analytics.

In the MUKA case, a platform with the mentioned functionalities will be applied to a specific scenario aiming to improve migration reporting, as well as restrict criminality and violence in the municipality of Katerini. News feeds and social media will be analysed while location specific information will be processed to evaluate the living conditions of immigrants and sense the local's acceptance and form privacy preserving groups of opinions and views. It is clear that also this ambitious DTA has several types of ethical, social and legal assessments of wide relevance, given the increasing emergence of the problem at global level and the close link with social and legal issues.

Following the discussions with the use case team, which includes CERTH co-author of the deliverable, and 2021.AI, we developed **4 indicators**:

- 3 computational indicators to enable **Continuous evaluation and improvement** and collecting in particular performance statistics on usage and frequency, as well as on statistics on impacts;
- 1 indicator addressing **Justice, equality and the rule of law** and consisting of a racial slur scanner.

The indicators dealing with *Continuous evaluation and improvement* can be easily applied to other use cases/DTA. The racial slur scanner, on the other hand, is relevant only for DTAs based on technologies that enable dialogue with users or where users can talk to each other (AI, robotics-

based), or possibly for socially relevant online document repositories (Big/Open Data-based). As this use case started from a fairly low level of maturity, the objectives and actions that will be put into practice in the next phase of the project, the piloting phase, are of utmost importance.

6. Practical use of the RDT Indicator Framework

The assessment process envisaged by ETAPAS in the use of its indicator framework starts from the context analysis methodology developed as part of Task 3.3 “Measurement systems stakeholder validation approach” and reported in Deliverable 3.3 “Validation method and guidelines”. In particular, this methodology involves an analysis of the context of the specific DTA, based on identified main drivers, the derivation from this analysis of a prioritization of ethical issues and risk areas identified by ETAPAS and the definition of tailored computational indicators, as outlined by **Figure 8** below:

Figure 12: Overview of the validation process and focus on the Assessment Phase (see D3.3)

The following sections will describe **Step 3** of the assessment phase, presenting how this step should be accomplished and specifically describing how to complete the assessment, how scores are calculated, how results are presented and, finally, how to interpret them. In addition, a more detailed description of the last step of the assessment phase and of the scoring system can be found in Deliverable 3.2 “Measurement guidelines”.

How to complete the assessment?

The use case owner, collecting inputs from relevant stakeholders, **answers the 25 risk indicators** from the RDT Indicator Framework. From the overall risk score obtained, it becomes clear how risky in general the DTA is to be considered. In addition, once answered to the risk indicators, **only the still relevant mitigation indicators will need to be answered**. At this point, the use case owner can either answer to all of them and evaluate the overall mitigation score or start answering the ones associated with the risk categories with heavier weights. This second approach can be especially useful in planning the most urgent risk mitigation actions to be implemented.

Furthermore, it is important to note that, in line with ETAPAS's goal of making the tool accessible to public sector organizations and their employees, a number of additional tools have been developed to support the undertaking of the assessment. First of all, for each indicator **guidelines** are provided, which give indications on how correctly interpret the indicator in terms of aim, context of applicability and how to choose the most appropriate answers. Secondly, for each indicator, the most **relevant stakeholders** are listed to support the specific assessment, who can be either directly undertaking the assessment or contacted by the person conducting the assessment to provide useful input or feedback. Thirdly, within the framework there is a detailed **glossary** sheet, which provides definitions

and explanations of acronyms and represents an additional tool to support the correct interpretation of indicators.

How are scores calculated?

On the basis of the analysis of the context and the resulting **prioritisation of the ETAPAS risk categories** the risk categories identified as more relevant and dangerous for the use case/DTA will have higher weights than those whose risks are unlikely to occur. Risk category weights are calculated in percentage terms, as detailed in **Section 3.1.3 of D3.3**. When the use case owner fills in the 25 risk indicators by selecting the answer that reflects the situation of the use case/DTA, each possible answer is associated with a specific score ranging from 1 to 5, where 1 represents the minimum level of risk exposure and 5 the maximum. At this point, **the risk score is calculated by multiplying the score associated to the selected answer to the risk indicator by the weight of the corresponding risk category in the context of the specific DTA/use case** (weighted mean). Finally, the score is translated into a percentage of the maximum possible value.

Then, the use case owner compiles the mitigation indicators. Likewise for risk indicators, to every possible answer is associated a determined score that goes from 1 to 5. In the case of the mitigation indicators, however, a higher score represents a more effective mitigation of the risk, so that 5 will represent fully mitigated risks in line with best practices, while 1 the absence of mitigation actions. This is because in a semantic way, a higher “risk score” represents a riskier DTA, while a higher “mitigation score” represents a better mitigation of the risk and then a safer DTA. **The mitigation score is then calculated by multiplying the score associated to the selected answer to the mitigation indicator by the weight of the corresponding risk category in the context of the specific DTA/use case** (weighted mean). Finally, also the mitigation score is translated into a percentage of its maximum possible value.

How to interpret the results?

The risk score and the mitigation score shall not be interpreted separately. In particular, **the risk score determines the acceptability brackets for the mitigation score**. This is because it is clear that the riskier is a use case/DTA, the more crucial it is that effective risk mitigation actions are implemented. Acceptability brackets depend also on the maximum possible mitigation score, which varies on the basis of the answers to the leading risk indicator and the implementation stage the specific use case/DTA is in. In fact, some answers to risk indicators determine the omission of some of the corresponding mitigation indicators, while some mitigation indicators are specific to some of the implementation phases of the use case/DTA. More specifically, **acceptability brackets are calculated in quartiles based on the risk score and on the specific maximum mitigation score foreseen by the particular assessment configuration**.

Therefore, for a given assessment configuration:

- provided that the **risk score is $\geq 90\%$** , the **mitigation score should be at least $\geq 80\%$** for the DTA to be acceptably safe;
- provided that the **risk score is $\geq 75\%$** , the **mitigation score should be at least $\geq 65\%$** for the DTA to be acceptably safe;
- provided that the **risk score is $\geq 50\%$** , the **mitigation score should be at least $\geq 50\%$** for the DTA to be acceptably safe;
- provided that the **risk score is $< 50\%$** , the **mitigation score should be at least $\geq 40\%$** for the DTA to be acceptably safe.

Based on the acceptability bracket for the mitigation actions and the risk score, the use case/DTA is considered acceptably safe or not acceptably safe. Furthermore, the platform will be able to identify the individual mitigation indicators on which the use case/DTA scored lowest (e.g. 1) and provide suggestions for mitigation actions in that specific area.

How will the results be presented?

We expect the results to be presented in the Grace platform **results dashboard** both at the end of the risk assessment and at the end of the mitigation assessment. This means that already after answering the 25 risk indicators, the platform user will have the possibility to check the **risk score** obtained, so that if it is very high, he can choose not to continue and change some characteristics of the use case/DTA before undertaking the assessment a second time. Once the mitigation indicators section has been completed, the results dashboard will be updated so as to contain the **risk and the mitigation scores, whether the DTA is acceptably safe or not and suggested mitigation actions for each risk category**. As showed by **Figure 13** below, the risk and mitigation scores are reported both in percentage and in absolute terms. Moreover, the results dashboard will contain a section per each risk category showing how the DTA scored with respect to the corresponding mitigation actions.

Figure 13: Example of a results dashboard

Furthermore, since the assessment is to be performed more than once during the DTA life cycles, aggregated results will be shown in the **overall results dashboard**, where the results of each assessment carried out in the various stages of DTA/use case implementation will be shown on a timeline, as exemplified by Figure 14 below.

Figure 14: Example of an overall results dashboard

7. Conclusion and next steps

This document aims at providing a description and analysis of the RDT Indicator Framework at the current stage of the project research. The present deliverable, together with D3.2 “Measurement guidelines” providing details and guidelines concerning the interpretation and measurement of the indicators, are the foundations on which the following phase of the project will be based. In particular, during the “Test & Validation” phase, four real-life use cases will be carried out by the PS organisations members of the ETAPAS consortium together with their technical partners. The main objective of Phase 2 is therefore to test the RDT Framework by applying the validation methodology explained in D3.3 to both allow the development of the ETAPAS prototypical platform and refine all the components of the RDT Framework. Indeed, in Phase 3 - Synthesis & Impact pathways of the project, lesson learned from use cases implementation will be analysed and a Governance model will be designed aimed at managing, by design, the ethical risks throughout the life-cycle of a DTA and considering its social and legal aspects. This iterative approach was already foreseen during the project definition, but it was also requested by our partners during the last consultation we carried out. This makes it clear that what we developed in this initial phase and is presented here is just a first step towards the improved and final version of the RDT Framework as part of the Governance model.

The Testing & Validation Phase will be of uttermost importance to understand if the results of our research are also practical, feasible and fit for the purpose of DT adoption in the PS. Indeed, our last consultation showed that the indicator framework is clear and gives practical insights on how to mitigate the risks of DT adoption. We also asked our use cases’ team members to provide an overall opinion on the relevance and feasibility of the assessment indicators. The results show that nobody thinks that the indicators are not relevant for his/her use case, and 3 out of the 7 respondents thinks that they are also easy to answer.

Finally, also based on the results of our last consortium consultation, we identified **7 key areas for future development and research** for the improvement of the RDT Indicator Framework, which are as follows:

- **Testing the scoring methodology** for both risk and mitigation indicators with real data during the pilots in order to define the best and most suitable approach;
- **Detailing and integrating computational indicators** also identifying sub-indicators, datasets requirements and data connectors;
- **Analysing technology specificity for the indicators** by exploiting the test phase with the ETAPAS use cases to identify how to further differentiate the indicators and their guidelines

and by analysing additional assessments for those DTs that had less priority for the ETAPAS project (e.g. blockchain, IoT, VR/AR);

- **Assessing social impacts of DTs** through for example quality of life or well-being indicators, also tailored to the specific ETAPAS use case;
- **Integrating the RDT Framework in the prototypical platform** so that it could enable a smooth undertaking of the assessment by any Public Sector intended user;
- **Improving the process and the relation with the legal assessment**, since we identified some potential overlapping between the legal assessment methodology that UniGraz is developing;
- **Translating to local languages** such as French, Italian, Norwegian and Greek.

8. Annex 1: Analysed Best Practices

This annex includes a description of all the frameworks that were analysed for the ETAPAS Indicator Framework. The frameworks presented include ways of assessing different types of Disruptive Technologies (DTs) such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), Robotics, etc. These frameworks include indicators for risks that might a company face when adopting a DTA, while also include mitigation actions and best practises that could be followed. Before the analysis of the frameworks, it needs to be mentioned that the frameworks were initially examined in order to discover the features used in each framework and the notion followed, and then we proceeded to the design of the RDT framework.

For the implementation of the ETAPAS Indicator Framework, data, questions, examples, best practices, concepts, definitions, and risks were obtained from all the following frameworks, depending on the type and purpose of each one of them. These frameworks contain information on all technologies included in the concept of Disruptive Technologies (DTs) such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), Robotics, Big data, etc.

All frameworks were initially analysed one by one in order to specify and define the risks that need to be included in the ETAPAS Indicator Framework, and then each risk category was analysed on its own in order to define the risk indicators, mitigation indicators, best practices, etc .

8.1. High-Level Expert Group (HLEG) - Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI)

Key information

- Source link: [Direct Link](#)
- Target audience: AI designers and AI developers of the AI system; data scientists; procurement officers or specialists; front-end staff that will use or work with the AI system; legal/compliance officers; management.
- Main objective / focus area: The HLEG Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI) is a practical tool that helps business and organisations self-assess the trustworthiness of their Artificial Intelligence (AI) systems under development in light with the Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI⁵.

Brief description

The aim of the HLEG Assessment List is to promote Trustworthy AI. This Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (ALTAI) is intended for self-evaluation purposes. It provides an initial approach for the evaluation of Trustworthy AI. It builds on the one outlined in the Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI and was developed over a period of two years, from June 2018 to June 2020.

⁵ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>

Detailed description

In 2019 the High-Level Expert Group (HLEG) on Artificial Intelligence (AI HLEG), set up by the European Commission, published the Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence. This guideline aims to offer guidance on securing ethical and robust AI. Addressed to all stakeholders, these Guidelines seek to go beyond a list of ethical principles, by providing guidance on how such principles can be operationalized in sociotechnical systems. This framework is composed of three layers of abstraction, called chapters. The first chapter is more abstract since it includes key guidance for the development, deployment and utilization of AI systems in a way that adheres to the ethical principles of: respect for human autonomy, prevention of harm, fairness and explicability. The second chapter offers guidance on the implementation and realization of Trustworthy AI by providing a list of seven requirements that should be met from both technical and non-technical methods.

The third chapter of those Guidelines contained an Assessment List to help assess whether the AI system that is being developed, deployed, procured or used, adheres to the seven requirements of Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (AI), as specified in our Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI:

- Human agency and oversight
- Technical Robustness and safety
- Privacy and data governance
- Transparency
- Diversity, Non-discrimination and Fairness
- Societal and environmental well-being
- Accountability

Based on these guidelines and the requirements set, the Assessment List (ALTAI) has been implemented for self-evaluation purposes. It is intended for flexible use: organisations can draw on elements relevant to the particular AI system from this Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (ALTAI) or add elements to it as they see fit, taking into consideration the sector they operate in. It helps organisations understand what Trustworthy AI is, in particular what risks an AI system might generate, and how to minimize those risks while maximising the benefit of AI. It is intended to help organisations identify how proposed AI systems might generate risks, and to identify whether and what kind of active measures may need to be taken to avoid and minimise those risks.

The ALTAI is completed and could be from within and/or outside an organisation with specific competences or expertise on each of the 7 requirements and related questions. For each requirement, it provides introductory guidance and relevant definitions in the Glossary, along with explanations for requirement's scope, explanatory notes for many of the questions.

How was the framework useful for the ETAPAS Indicator Framework

The HLEG Assessment List was used as the basis of the ETAPAS Indicator Framework along with other frameworks. The framework introduced key requirements that are valuable for the ETAPAS Indicator Framework as they covered the framework's major risk categories concerning the direct interaction with humans, governance and legal risks, errors and misuse issues, security, and privacy concerns along with requirements set for inequality and discrimination.

Since the HLEG Assessment List is flexible, elements have been drawn concerning the risk categories related and defined within the ETAPAS Indicator Framework, including questions and mitigation actions for each of the key requirements. The ETAPAS Indicator Framework has adopted the ethical principles of the HLEG Assessment List, and also used some of the risk questions and mitigation actions referred to the 7 key requirements of the HLEG Assessment List.

8.2. World Economic Forum (WEF) AI Governance framework

Key information

- Source link: [Direct link](#)
- Target audience: organizations that procure and deploy AI solutions and organizations that would like to use AI to improve their operational efficiency.
- Main objective / focus area: The World Economic Forum (WEF) AI Governance framework aims to provide guidance to organizations deploying AI at scale on how to do so in a responsible manner

Brief description

In collaboration with the World Economic Forum Centre for the Fourth Industrial Revolution, the Info-communications Media Development Authority (IMDA) and Personal Data Protection Commission (PDPC) have developed an Implementation and Self-Assessment Guide for Organizations (ISAGO), a companion to complement the voluntary Model AI Governance Framework⁶. The Model Framework translates ethical principles into implementable practices, applicable to a common AI deployment process. This framework focuses primarily on four broad areas: internal governance structures and measures, human involvement in AI-augmented decision-making, operations management and stakeholder interaction and communication. Additionally, this framework provides guidance on the key issues to be considered and measures that can be implemented and terms and definitions that are useful for AI governance.

Detailed description

This framework includes four main areas concerning:

- internal governance structures and measures
- operations management
- guidance for stakeholder's interaction and communication
- the level of human involvement in AI-augmented decision-making

Each one of the areas includes guiding questions along with useful industry examples, practices and guides for consideration that can be taken into account according to the target audience. Guiding questions for limited scenarios are also presented, thus giving readers the opportunity to have additional questions as well as examples and practices for scenarios that may be limited and relevant with them.

Both the questions and the examples given are explanatory, aiming at the best provision of information but also at the optimization of the procedures of each area.

How was the framework useful for the ETAPAS Indicator Framework

The main areas included in the WEF AI Governance framework are an important element for the ETAPAS Indicator Framework, as they contribute to its comprehensive presentation, and include important risks.

From the WEF AI Governance framework, the ETAPAS Indicator Framework has received multiple questions referring in the common risk categories of the two frameworks, questions about scenarios

⁶<https://www.pdpc.gov.sg/-/media/Files/PDPC/PDF-Files/Resource-for-Organisation/AI/SGModelAIGovFramework2.pdf>

that might be limited but useful for the ETAPAS project's context, and best practices and examples that were included in the recommendation section of the ETAPAS Indicator Framework.

8.3. NOREA Guiding Principles Trustworthy AI investigation

Key information

- Source link: [Direct link](#)
- Target audience: IT-auditors that would like to receive information for on enterprise artificially intelligent algorithmic systems based on leading practices for Trustworthy AI.
- Main objective / focus area: The document presents the Guiding Principles for Trustworthy AI investigations developed by NOREA, the Dutch Association of chartered IT-auditors. These principles were developed to guide Dutch chartered IT-auditors (RE's) in conducting investigations of algorithmic systems based on leading practices for Trustworthy AI.

Brief description

The Guiding Principles included in NOREA framework aim to support IT-auditors in performing ex-ante and/or ex-post investigations of algorithmic systems to guide and support organizations in their journey towards deploying trustworthy AI applications. The Guiding Principles are structured according to the Cross Industry Standard Process for Data Mining (CRISP-DM) and were developed by the Expert Committee Algorithm Assurance of NOREA in 2020-2021.

Detailed description

The framework contains 119 key considerations for Trustworthy AI investigations, categorized into 5 risk categories and 6 CRISP-DM phases and an added Governance phase. The **CRISP-DM phases** are:

- Business Understanding
- Data Understanding
- Data Preparation
- Modelling
- Evaluation
- Deployment

The **risk indicators** are:

- Governance
- Ethics
- Privacy
- Performance
- Security

For each phase of the CRISP-DM process, the aforementioned risk categories were established that are relevant to the correct functioning of algorithmic systems. Various public, private, and civil organizations have produced frameworks for these risk categories. The NOREA Expert Committee Algorithm Assurance has reviewed a range of these frameworks with the objective to select a comprehensive and accepted industry standard in the European context. Each risk category includes several key questions for the IT-auditor to raise, all related to control objectives and measures.

For the guiding principles and each of their corresponding risk categories, a reference to applicable laws, regulations, frameworks, and standards is provided along with key questions that the reader has to consider. Examples of checks to perform and/or evidence to look for while investigating a risk category are also made available, aiming to present mitigation actions that could be applied for each risk category. The questions included in NOREA were derived from the following laws, regulations and leading practices:

- ISO 240281^[1] and 270012^[2]
- European Commission AI High Level Expert Group: Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI^[3]
- General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)^[4]
- Information Commissioner's Office Guidance on the AI Auditing Framework^[5]
- COBIT^[6]

Figure 15: Structure of NOREA Guiding Principles for Trustworthy AI investigations^[7]

How was the framework useful for the ETAPAS Indicator Framework

NOREA framework is based on 5 risk categories and includes both risk questions, for each category, and best practices for each question. The inspiration for the use of the NOREA framework came from the different indicators supported in it and from the way they are constructed in different phases. This feature was a basic idea for the order in which the questions are asked in the ETAPAS Indicator Framework. Additionally, the ETAPAS Indicator Framework has adopted from the NOREA framework multiple questions from all its risk categories (i.e. governance, ethics, privacy, performance, and security) and also some of the best practices for each of these questions.

8.4. UK Gov. Data Ethics framework

Key information

- Source link: Direct link or <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/data-ethics-framework>
- Target audience: Public servants (government and wider public sector) working with data
- Main objective / focus area: Ethical data use

Brief description

The UK Gov. Data Ethics Framework was created by the Department for Digital, Culture, Media and Sport (DCMS) and Government Digital Service (GDS) of the United Kingdom. It is designed to guide

appropriate and responsible data use in government and the wider public sector projects, being aimed at anyone working directly or indirectly with data in the public sector.

Detailed description

The UK Gov. Data Ethics Framework assessment approach is organized into **three overarching principles** that are applicable throughout the entire process and underpin all actions and all aspects of the project:

- Transparency
- Accountability
- Fairness

as well as into **five specific actions**:

1. Define public benefit and user needs
2. Involve diverse expertise
3. Comply with the law
4. Check the quality and limitations of the data
 - 4.1. Check the quality and limitations of the model
5. Evaluate and consider wider policy implications

The actions are designed to guide through different stages of the project and provide practical considerations. The assessment of each of the specific actions is further divided into sub-actions (for better understanding). Questions are provided for each sub-action as a guide through the ethical considerations in the project (guiding questions).

More specifically:

1. Define public benefit and user need is divided into:

1. *Public benefit*: Understand the wider public benefit
2. *Public benefit*: Understand unintended and or negative consequences of your project (pertains to the *Fairness* principle)
3. *Public benefit*: Human rights considerations (pertains to the *Fairness* principle)
4. *Public benefit*: Justify the benefit for the taxpayers and appropriate use of public resources in your project (pertains to the *Accountability* principle)
5. *Public benefit*: Make your user need and public benefit transparent (pertains to the *Transparency* principle)
6. *User need*: Understand the user need
7. *User need*: Ensure there is a clear articulation of the problem before you start the project
8. *User need*: Check if everyone in your team understands the user need and how using data can help
9. *User need*: Repeatedly revisit your user need throughout the project

2. Involve diverse expertise

1. Get the right expertise
2. Ensure diversity within your team (pertains to the *Fairness* principle)
3. Involve external stakeholders

4. Effective governance structures with experts (pertains to the *Accountability* principle)
5. *Transparency*

3. Comply with the law

1. Get legal advice
2. It is your duty and obligation to obey the law in any data projects. You must ensure the project's compliance with GDPR and DPA 2018 (pertains to the *Accountability* principle)
3. Data protection by design and DPIA
4. *Accountability*
5. *Transparency*
6. Ensure the project's compliance with the Equality Act 2010 (pertains to the *Fairness* principle)
7. Ensure effective governance of your data
8. Ensure your project's compliance with any additional regulations

4. Check the quality and limitations of the data

1. Data source
2. Determining proportionality
3. Bias in data (pertains to the *Fairness* principle)
4. Data anonymization
5. Robust practices (pertains to the *Accountability* principle)
6. Make your data open and shareable whenever possible (pertains to the *Transparency* principle)

4.1 Check the quality and limitations of the model

7. Share your models - developed data science tools should be made available for scrutiny wherever possible (pertains to the *Transparency* principle)
8. How to ensure transparency of sensitive models (pertains to the *Transparency* principle)
9. Explainability (pertains to the *Transparency* principle)

5. Evaluate and consider wider policy implications

1. Evaluate the project (pertains to the *Accountability* principle)
2. Repeatedly revisit the user need and public benefit throughout the project (pertains to the *Fairness* principle)
3. Check how your project influences policy (pertains to the *Fairness* principle)
4. Ensure there are skills, training, maintenance for longevity of the project
5. Accountability structures (pertains to the *Accountability* principle)
6. Public scrutiny (pertains to the *Accountability* principle)
7. Share your learnings (pertains to the *Transparency* principle)

The total of the answers constitutes a data ethics assessment. The framework uses a self-assessment scoring scale to help with the identification of the aspects of the project that need further work. This scoring is performed on a 0-5 scale with the lowest value (0) meaning that the information about the

project, its methods, and outcomes is not publicly available and the highest value (5) meaning that the aforementioned information are widely available to the public. In the case when a 3 or less is scored for a project in any of the principles it indicates the need for additional checks and potential changes to make the project more ethical.

Each part of the framework is designed to be regularly revisited throughout a project, especially when any changes are made to the data collection, storage, analysis, or sharing processes. Teams of data practitioners, policymakers, operational staff, and those helping to produce data-informed insight should work through the framework together ex-ante, during, and ex-post the implementation of a project.

How was the framework useful for the ETAPAS Indicator Framework

The UK Gov. Data Ethics framework is one of the frameworks that were used as a basis for the ETAPAS Indicator Framework. This framework includes several risk and mitigation indicators in the form of question that were adopted by the ETAPAS Indicator Framework.

From the context of the UK Gov. Data Ethics framework, the basic principles were taken and their context was examined and reviewed, so that the risk and mitigation indicators could be properly adapted within the context of the ETAPAS Indicator Framework. Moreover, the practice of evaluating the project before the start (ex-ante), during and after (ex-post) that was adopted in the ETAPAS Indicator Framework is based on the UK Gov. Data Ethics framework.

8.5. The UK Gov. & Alan Turing Institute's AI ethics and safety guidance

Key information

- Source link: Direct link and https://www.turing.ac.uk/sites/default/files/2019-06/understanding_artificial_intelligence_ethics_and_safety.pdf
- Target audience: Department and delivery leads in the public sector deciding whether AI is the right solution in their project and looking for information on how to use AI safely and ethically.
- Main objective / focus area: Ethics and safety for the responsible design and implementation of AI systems in the public sector

Brief description

The UK Gov. AI ethics and safety guidance was created by the Office for Artificial Intelligence (OAI) and the Government Digital Service (GDS) in partnership with The Alan Turing Institute's [public policy programme](#) (United Kingdom). It provides the conceptual resources and practical tools that aim to enable oversight of the responsible design and implementation of AI projects.

Detailed description

In the scope of the UK Gov. AI ethics and safety guidance framework, three building-blocks necessary to provide an ethical platform are defined:

The **SUM Values** that are ethical values that

- Support
- Underwrite
- Motivate

a responsible data design and use ecosystem and they will be composed of four key notions:

- Respect
- Connect
- Care
- Protect

The objectives of these SUM Values are to:

- provide an accessible framework to start thinking about the moral scope of the societal and ethical impacts of a project and
- establish well-defined criteria to evaluate the ethical permissibility of the project.

The **FAST Track Principles**, composed of four key notions (principles):

- Fairness
- Accountability
- Sustainability
- Transparency

These aim to provide the moral and practical tools that:

- ensure that project is bias-mitigating, non-discriminatory, and fair, and
- safeguard public trust in your project’s capacity to deliver safe and reliable AI innovation

A **process-based governance** framework (PBG Framework) that operationalises the SUM Values and the FAST Track Principles across the entire AI project delivery workflow. The objective of this PBG Framework is to set up transparent processes of design and implementation that safeguard and enable the justifiability of both the AI project and its product.

Figure 16: The three building-blocks necessary to provide an ethical platform as defined by the UK Gov AI ethics and safety guidance; SUM Values, FAST Track Principles and PBG Framework

This framework offers specific guidelines to be used in the processes of:

- Establishing a Process-Based Governance Framework, i.e., good governance practices to guide the strategy of building out responsible AI project workflow processes
- Ensuring the transparency of the outcome of an AI project, i.e., defining, designing, and delivering a sufficiently interpretable AI system

- Securing responsible delivery through human-centred implementation protocols and practices

How was the framework useful for the ETAPAS Indicator Framework

The UK Gov. Data Ethics framework is one of the principal frameworks used as the basis of the ETAPAS Indicator Framework. This framework includes definitions of the main principles described, examples and descriptions about the guidelines that can be used in order to form an ethical AI system.

The key notions (principles): Fairness, Accountability, Sustainability and Transparency, adopted in this framework were also incorporated into the ETAPAS Indicator Framework. Additionally, the framework was used in conjunction with the other frameworks for the risk questions & mitigation actions, particularly regarding the *Responsibility and Accountability* and *Transparency and Explainability* principles of the ETAPAS Indicator Framework. Lastly, *Guidelines* for designing, implementing, and deploying interpretable AI systems presented in the framework will be incorporated in the ETAPAS Indicator Framework's guidelines.

8.6. UK Gov. A guide to using artificial intelligence in the public sector

Key information

- Source link: [Direct link](#)
- Target audience: public sector organisations
- Main objective / focus area: Guiding public sector on building and using artificial intelligence.

Brief description

This guide aims to provide information and guidance on using AI in the public sector, provided by the UK Gov.

Detailed description

The Government Digital Service (GDS) and the Office for Artificial Intelligence (OAI) have published joint guidance on how to build and use artificial intelligence (AI) in the public sector. The guide includes information on how to assess if the AI will help the public sector meet user needs, the best practices of using AI in the public sector and guidelines on how to implement AI ethically, fairly and safely. The guide also includes the steps that the public sector should take to plan and prepare before implementing AI. It includes descriptions, examples, and best practices along with useful material explaining how AI can be used in the public sector along with common applications.

How was the framework useful for the ETAPAS Indicator Framework

The guide to using artificial intelligence in the public sector provided by the UK Gov. was a useful tool for analysis when designing the ETAPAS Indicator Framework. This guide does include neither question referring to risks of AI nor mitigation actions, however it includes guides information and explanation of how the AI can be used in the public sector.

The key idea of using AI in the public sector along with the information provided in this guide, were used for the enhancement of the guidelines included in the ETAPAS Indicator Framework.

8.7. The ICO AI and Data Protection Risk Toolkit

Key information

- Source link: [Direct link](#)
- Target audience: firstly, those with a compliance focus, including: data protection officers (DPOs), general counsel, risk managers, senior management; and the ICO's (Information Commissioner's Office) own auditors and secondly, technology specialists including: machine-learning developers and data scientists, software developers/engineers, and cybersecurity and IT risk managers.
- Main objective / focus area: Personal Data. This framework provides a clear methodology to audit AI applications and ensure personal data is processed in compliance with the law.

Brief description

The ICO AI and Data Protection Risk Toolkit work is based on the [Guidance on AI and Data Protection on Explaining Decisions Made With AI](#) (The Alan Turing Institute & ICO) and is also part of the ICO commitment to [enable good data protection practice in AI](#).

Detailed description

The ICO AI and Data Protection Risk Toolkit reflects the auditing framework developed by the ICO internal assurance and investigation teams. This framework provides a methodology to audit AI applications and ensure they process personal data in compliance with the law. The toolkit covers best practices for data protection-compliant AI. If an organization is using AI to process personal data, then by following this toolkit, high assurance of being compliant with data protection legislation is guaranteed.

The ICO AI and Data Protection Risk Toolkit follows **four stages of the AI lifecycle**:

- Business requirements and design
- Data acquisition and preparation
- Training and testing
- Deployment and monitoring

And **eight risk domain areas**:

- Accountability and governance
- Lawfulness and purpose limitation
- Fairness (Statistical accuracy, bias and discrimination)
- Transparency
- Security
- Data Minimisation
- Individual rights
- Meaningful human review

The toolkit contains risk statements to help organisations using AI to process personal data understand the risks to individuals' information rights. Each risk statement pertains simultaneously to one of the AI lifecycle-stages and one risk domain area and points to one or more practical steps, i.e., best practices, for the mitigation of the risk and law compliance.

How was the framework useful for the ETAPAS Indicator Framework

The ICO framework was reviewed while designing the ETAPAS Indicator Framework aiming to detect new risk domain areas that were not included in the ETAPAS Indicator Framework.

According to this review, it was pointed that the notions of the *risk category* adopted in the ETAPAS Indicator Framework is analogous to the one of *risk domain area* used in The ICO AI and Data Protection Risk Toolkit. Similarly, the notion of the *mitigation indicator* is analogous to *practical steps/best practices*. Moreover, this toolkit's best practices will be used in formulation of the corresponding guidelines in the ETAPAS Indicator Framework.

Within the ETAPAS Indicator Framework, the best practices of the ICO framework were used as guidelines and the framework itself was also used in combination with other frameworks for the extraction of risk and mitigation indicators.

8.8. Robot Impact Assessment (ROBIA)

Key information

- Source link: [Direct link^{\[8\]} \[9\]](#)
- Target audience: robot engineers
- Main objective / focus area: Guide robot engineers in the process of identifying the legal aspects associated with the robotics technology.

Brief description

The ROBIA involves setting the context, describing the robot, identifying the relevant framework, identifying the risks, and mitigating them. Following ROBIA, robot engineers may identify relevant safeguards to make robots safe in every respect. In the Annex, I provide roboticists with a ROBIA model.

Detailed description

ROBIA concerns ethical, legal, and societal consequences, instrumental to R&D in different stages: idea/concept/design, prototyping and testing/experimenting, post-launch. Furthermore, ROBIA includes all the information concerning impacts and mitigation actions that should be followed by robot engineers along with all separate assessments for every impact a particular robot technology may pose (e.g., data protection, surveillance, environmental).

How was the framework useful for the ETAPAS Indicator Framework

The questions and steps included in this paper have been used to enhance the ETAPAS Indicator Framework concerning the indicators referring to the robotics field, in conjunction with the questions and definitions provided in the “Conducting a Robot Impact Assessment” paper. Alongside, explanations included in the guidelines referring to the ex-ante and ex-post technology regulation were adopted.

8.9. Conducting a Robot Impact Assessment paper

Key information

- Source link: [Direct link](#)
- Target audience: organizations developing or using robotics, roboticists

- Main objective / focus area: Assessment of the robot's impact

Brief description

This paper presents the methods for assessing robot's impact.

Detailed description

This paper presents a methodology for the Robot Impact Assessment (ROBIA). This methodology helps roboticists to identify, analyze and mitigate the legal risks associated with robot technology. The paper describes the different steps that need to be covered when assessing a robot, while it includes also questions relevant with the legal framework and the risks existing when using or developing a robot. The questions of this paper are additional with the guide presented in section 9.8.

How was the framework useful for the ETAPAS Indicator Framework

This paper mainly includes questions about the risks included in ROBIA. The questions and steps included in this paper have been used to enhance the ETAPAS Indicator Framework concerning the indicators referring to the field of robotics.

8.10. National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) Framework for Improving Critical Infrastructure Cybersecurity

Key information

- Source link: [Direct link](#)
- Target audience: cybersecurity engineers and related stakeholders, infrastructure owners and operators
- Main objective / focus area: Identify and develop cybersecurity risk framework for all related parties.

Brief description

The NIST aims to include identifying and developing cybersecurity risk frameworks for voluntary use by critical infrastructure owners and operators. NIST must identify “a prioritized, flexible, repeatable, performance-based, and cost-effective approach, including information security measures and controls that may be voluntarily adopted by owners and operators of critical infrastructure to help them identify, assess, and manage cyber risks.” ^[10]

Detailed description

The NIST Framework focuses on using business drivers to guide cybersecurity activities and considering cybersecurity risks as part of the organization's risk management processes. The Framework consists of three parts: the Framework Core, the Implementation Tiers, and the Framework Profiles. The Framework Core is a set of cybersecurity activities, outcomes, and informative references that are common across sectors and critical infrastructure. Elements of the Core provide detailed guidance for developing individual organizational Profiles. Through use of Profiles, the Framework will help an organization to align and prioritize its cybersecurity activities with its business/mission requirements, risk tolerances, and resources. The Tiers provide a

mechanism for organizations to view and understand the characteristics of their approach to managing cybersecurity risk, which will help in prioritizing and achieving cybersecurity objectives^[11].

How was the framework useful for the ETAPAS Indicator Framework

The NIST framework includes risks and examples that should be followed when designing a system, aiming to cover any cybersecurity risks that might rise. The NIST framework was analysed for the cybersecurity risks included in it, which could be used by the ETAPAS Indicator Framework. The risks and examples referred in the NIST concerning cybersecurity and data were taken into consideration during the design of the guidelines of the ETAPAS Indicator Framework. More specifically, the examples presented in NIST were included in the guidelines referring to cybersecurity on the ETAPAS Indicator Framework.

9. Annex 2: RDT Indicator Framework Charts

Percentage (%) of risk indicators per principle

- Safety and security (P5)
- Justice, equality, and the rule of law (P2)
- Responsibility and accountability (P4)
- Continuous evaluation and improvement (P10)
- Privacy (P6)
- Building an ethical culture involving employees (P7)
- Environmental sustainability (P1)
- Ethical public-private cooperation (P9)
- Transparency and explainability (P3)
- Retaining human contacts (P8)

Percentage (%) of mitigation indicators per principle

Figure 17: Pie charts presenting the percentage of both risk and mitigation indicators per principle.

Percentage (%) of computational indicators per principle

Figure 18: The percentages of the computational indicators defined per principle

Figure 19: A heatmap of ethical principles against risk categories

Figure 21: A mapping of assessment mitigation indicators against related risks, a value of 1 (marked with green) signifies the association of the indicator with the related risk, a value of 0 (marked with grey) indicates no defined association.

10. Annex 3: Glossary

Acronym	Extended term	Definition	Source
	Accessibility	Accessibility refers to the extent to which products, systems, services, environments and facilities can be used by people from a population with the widest range of user needs, characteristics and capabilities to achieve identified goals in identified contexts of use (which includes direct use or use supported by assistive technologies).	ALTAI - The Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
	Accuracy in a data protection	Accuracy in a data protection is a fundamental principle requiring to ensure that personal data is accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date. It requires to take all reasonable steps to make sure the personal data process is not 'incorrect or misleading as to any matter of fact' and, where necessary, is corrected or deleted without undue delay.	https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/pages/altai-assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence "
	Accuracy in AI/Machine Learning	The concept of accuracy in AI/ML is used to evaluate the predictive capability of the AI model. Informally, accuracy is the fraction of predictions the model got right. A number of metrics are used in machine learning (ML) to measure the predictive accuracy of a model. The choice of the accuracy metric to be used depends on the ML task.	General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)
	Accountability	This term refers to the idea that one is responsible for their action – and as a corollary their consequences – and must be able to explain their aims, motivations, and reasons. Accountability has several dimensions. Accountability is sometimes required by law and it might also express an ethical standard, and fall short of legal consequences.	ALTAI - The Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
	Adversarial Attack	An adversarial attack consists of subtly modifying the original data in such a way that the changes are almost undetectable, e.g. adversarial attacks on machine learning models maliciously modify input data to induce them into misclassification or incorrect prediction.	https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/pages/altai-assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence "
	Aggregation	Aggregation is a process whereby data is gathered and expressed in a summary form, especially for statistical analysis.	ICO framework & ALTAI - The Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
	AI designer	AI designer is a professional which support to bridge the gap between AI capabilities and user needs. For example, they can create prototypes showing some novel AI capabilities and how they might be used if the product is deployed, prior to	https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/pages/altai-assessment-list

		the possible development of the AI product. AI designers also work with development teams to better understand user needs and how to build technology that addresses those needs. Additionally, they can support AI developers by designing platforms to support data collection and annotation, ensuring that data collection respects some properties (such as safety and fairness).	trustworthy-artificial-intelligence"
	Anonymisation	Anonymisation consists in preventing any identification of individuals from personal data. The link between an individual and personal data is definitively erased.	https://medium.com/on-fido-tech/adversarial-attacks-and-defences-for-convolutional-neural-networks-66915ece52e7
AI	Artificial Intelligence	Artificial intelligence is linked to a system's ability to adapt and improve in a new context, to generalise its experiences and apply them to unfamiliar scenarios.	ALTAI - The Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
	Audit	An audit is an independent examination of some required properties of an entity, be it a company, a product, or a piece of software. Audits provide third-party assurance to various stakeholders that the subject matter is free from material misstatement. The term is most frequently applied to audits of the financial information relating to a legal person, but can be applied to anything else.	https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/pages/altai-assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence"
	Auditability	Auditability refers to the ability of an AI system to undergo the assessment of the system's algorithms, data and design processes. This does not necessarily imply that information about business models and Intellectual Property related to the AI system must always be openly available. Ensuring traceability and logging mechanisms from the early design phase of the AI system can help enable the system's auditability	ALTAI - The Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
AR	Augmented Reality	Augmented reality means superimposing an extra layer over the real-world environment, thus augmenting it. A perception of a physical, real-world environment enhanced with computer-generated sensory feedback such as voice, video, graphics, or GPS data is hence referred to as "augmented reality".	https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/pages/altai-assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence"
	Autonomous system	Autonomous systems are defined as systems that are able to accomplish a task, achieve a goal, or interact with its surroundings with minimal to no human involvement.	ALTAI - The Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
	Benchmarking	Benchmarking is the process of measuring key business metrics and practices and comparing	https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/pages/altai

		them—within business areas or against a competitor, industry peers, or other companies around the world—to understand how and where the organization needs to change in order to improve performance. Another definition of benchmarking mentions that it is the search for the best industry practices which will lead to exceptional performance through the implementation of these best practices	assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence "
	Bias	Bias can be defined as systematically and unfairly discriminating against certain individuals or groups of individuals in favor of others.	ETAPAS D2.1
	Black box system	Black box system is a system, device or object that can be viewed in terms of its inputs and outputs, without any knowledge of its internal workings.	ALTAI - The Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
	Blockchain	Blockchain is a system that allows an individual to track the sending and receiving of some types of information over the internet. These are pieces of code generated online that carry connected information – like blocks of data that form a chain	https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/pages/altai-assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence "
	Bug bounties	A bug bounty program is a deal offered by many websites, organizations and software developers by which individuals can receive recognition and compensation for reporting bugs, especially those pertaining to security exploits and vulnerabilities.	ALTAI - The Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
	Citizen scoring	Citizens scoring, also known as Social Credit System, is a combination of government and business surveillance that gives citizens a “score” that can restrict the ability of individuals to take actions — such as purchasing plane tickets, acquiring property or taking loans — because of behaviors.	https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/pages/altai-assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence "
CoC	Code of Conduct	A code of conduct is a statement of principles adopted by an organization to guide its own conduct. These principles can serve both as affirmations of values and as the basis of an internal accountability mechanism for the organization. Codes of conduct usually focus on ethical requirements and recommendations that go beyond what the law requires.	ETAPAS D2.1
	Competing interests	Competing interests refer to different values and interests that, at times, pull in different directions. Commonly referred to as ‘trade-offs’.	ALTAI - The Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
	Concept/model drift	In predictive analytics and machine learning, concept drift means that the statistical properties of the target variable, which the model is trying to predict, change over time in unforeseen ways. This	https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/pages/altai-assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence "

		causes problems because the predictions become less accurate as time passes.	trustworthy-artificial-intelligence"
	Confidence score	Much of AI involves estimating some quantity, such as the probability that the output is a correct answer to the given input. Confidence scores, or confidence intervals, are a way of quantifying the uncertainty of such an estimate. A low confidence score associated with the output of an AI system means that the system is not too sure that the specific output is correct.	Anand, G., & Kodali, R. (2008). Benchmarking the benchmarking models. <i>Benchmarking: An international journal</i> .
	Cost-benefit analysis	A cost-benefit analysis is the process of comparing the projected or estimated costs and benefits (or opportunities) associated with a project decision to determine whether it makes sense from a business perspective.	https://www.apqc.org/blog/what-are-four-types-benchmarking"
	Data governance	Data governance is a term used on both a macro and a micro level. On the macro level, data governance refers to the governing of cross-border data flows by countries, and hence is more precisely called international data governance. On the micro level, data governance is a data management concept concerning the capability that enables an organization to ensure that high data quality exists throughout the complete lifecycle of the data, and data controls are implemented that support business objectives. The key focus areas of data governance include data availability, usability, consistency, integrity, and sharing. It also regards establishing processes to ensure effective data management throughout the enterprise such as accountability for the adverse effects of poor data quality and ensuring that the data which an enterprise has can be used by the entire organization.	ETAPAS D2.4
	Data integrity	Data integrity is the process of maintaining and assuring the accuracy and consistency of data throughout the data lifecycle.	ICO framework
	Data poisoning	Data poisoning occurs when an adversarial actor attacks an AI system, and is able to inject bad data into the AI model’s training set, thus making the AI system learn something that it should not learn. Examples show that in some cases these data poisoning attacks on neural nets can be very effective, causing a significant drop in accuracy even with very little data poisoning. Other kinds of poisoning attacks do not aim to change the behavior of the AI system, but rather they insert a backdoor, which is a data that the model’s designer	ETAPAS D2.1

		is not aware of, but that the attacker can leverage to get the AI system to do what they want.	
	Data sampling	Data sampling is a statistical analysis technique used to select, manipulate and analyze a representative subset of data points to identify patterns and trends in the larger data set being examined.	ICO framework & https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bug_bounty_program
-	Developer	The developer is a professional that develops computer software	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Social_Credit_System
	De-identification techniques	De-identification is the process used to prevent a person’s identity from being connected with information. There are various techniques to apply de-identification. In most cases, deidentification is not anonymisation, but it’s still useful as a data minimisation technique.	ETAPAS D2.4
DT(s)	Disruptive Technology(s)	Disruptive technologies are the technologies with the potential to drastically alter the processes and operations in a particular field of both the public and private sectors. Companies in private organization adopt disruptive technologies for the automation of their tasks and the expansion of their services, aiming to increase their profit and be more competitive. Additionally, public sector takes steps in adopting disruptive technologies for the improvement of its procedures in order to automate time and resource consuming tasks.	ICO framework
DTA(s)	Disruptive Technology Application(s)	Disruptive Technology Application(s) are applications that have been implemented based on disruptive technologies.	ICO framework & https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Concept_drift
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment	DPIA is the evaluation of the effects that the processing of personal data might have on individuals to whom the data relates. A DPIA is necessary in cases in which the technology creates a high risk of violation of the rights and freedoms of individuals. The law requires a DPIA in case of automated processing, including profiling (i), processing of personal data revealing sensitive information like racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs (ii), processing of personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences (iii) and systematic monitoring of a publicly accessible area on a large scale (iv).	ALTAI - The Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
DPO	Data Protection Officer	This denotes an expert on data protection law. The function of a DPO is to internally monitor a public or private organisation’s compliance with GDPR. Public or private organisations must appoint DPOs	https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/pages/altai-assessment-list-

		in the following circumstances: (i) data processing activities are carried out by a public authority or body, except for courts acting in their judicial capacity; (ii) the processing of personal data requires regular and systematic monitoring of individuals on a large scale; (iii) the processing of personal data reveals sensitive information like racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or refers to criminal convictions and offences. A DPO must be independent of the appointing organisation.	trustworthy-artificial-intelligence"
	Data reliability	Data reliability means that data is complete and accurate, and meet the intended purposes, and are not subject to inappropriate alteration for building data trust across the organization.	https://online.hbs.edu/blog/post/cost-benefit-analysis
	Edge case	An edge case is a problem or situation that occurs only at an extreme (maximum or minimum) operating parameter. In programming, an edge case typically involves input values that require special handling in an algorithm.	ALTAI - The Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
	Encryption	Encryption is the procedure whereby clear text information is disguised by using especially a hash key. Encrypted results are unintelligible data for persons who do not have the encryption key.	https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/pages/altai-assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence"
	Equality	Equality aims to eliminate inequalities, and to promote equality, between men and women and to combat discrimination based on sex, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation.	https://digitalguardian.com/blog/what-data-integrity-data-protection-101
	Explainability	Explainability is a feature of an AI system that is intelligible to non-experts. An AI system is intelligible if its functionality and operations can be explained non-technically to a person not skilled in the art.	ALTAI - The Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
	Failsafe fallback plans	Failsafe fallback plans are an alternative set of actions and tasks available in the event that the primary plan needs to be abandoned because of issues, risks, or other causes.	https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/pages/altai-assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence"
	Fairness	Fairness refers to a variety of ideas known as equity, impartiality, egalitarianism, non-discrimination and justice. Fairness embodies an ideal of equal treatment between individuals or between groups of individuals.	https://searchbusinessanalytics.techtarget.com/definition/data-sampling

	Fairness (in data protection)	In a data protection context, ‘fairness’ means handling personal data in ways people reasonably expect and not use it in ways that have unjustified adverse effects on them.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Programmer
	Fault tolerance	Fault tolerance is the property that enables a system to continue operating properly in the event of the failure of (or one or more faults within) some of its components. If its operating quality decreases at all, the decrease is proportional to the severity of the failure, as compared to a naively designed system, in which even a small failure can cause total breakdown. Fault tolerance is particularly sought after in high-availability or safety critical systems. Redundancy or duplication is the provision of additional functional capabilities that would be unnecessary in a fault-free environment. This can consist of backup components that automatically ‘kick in’ if one component fails.	ICO framework
-	Final User	Final user refers to the person that is impacted by the decision taken by the DTA	ETAPAS D2.4
	Fit-for-purpose & sufficiency	The quantity of data collected or procured has a significant impact on the accuracy and reasonableness of the outputs of a trained model. Sufficiency and fit-for-purpose have to be determined by staff with technical and policy competencies.	ETAPAS consortium
	Generalization	Generalization refers to the model's ability to adapt properly to new, previously unseen data, drawn from the same distribution as the one used to create the model.	ALTAI - The Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
	High dimensional data	High dimensional data refers to a dataset in which the number of features is larger than the number of observations.	https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/pages/altai-assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence "
HOTL	Human-on-the-loop	Human-on-the-loop refers to the capability for human intervention during the design cycle of the system and monitoring the system’s operation	ALTAI - The Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
HITL	Human-in-the-loop	Human-in-the-loop refers to the capability for human intervention in every decision cycle of the system. Consider a human-in-the-loop approach when human judgement is able to significantly improve the quality of the decision made (e.g. pricing recommendation of million-dollar commodity bids) or when a human subjective	https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/pages/altai-assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence "

		judgment is required (e.g. market share forecasting for long-term decisions).	
	Human-out-of-the-loop	Human-out-of-the-loop refers to the functionality of the DTA to execute solutions without human intervention, input or interaction. Consider a human-out-of-the-loop approach when it is not practical to subject every algorithmic recommendation to a human review.	https://itlaw.wikia.org/wiki/Data_reliability
	Human-over-the-loop	On the human-over-the-loop approach, the human supervises the system and can intervene whenever the AI system runs into an unexpected scenario and deviates from its performance standard. Consider a human-over-the-loop approach to allow humans to intervene when the situation calls for it. To achieve this, organizations could consider using statistical confidence levels to determine when human is required to intervene.	ICO framework
	Humanoid robot	Humanoid robots are professional service robots built to mimic human motion and interaction. Like all service robots, they provide value by automating tasks in a way that leads to cost-savings and productivity. In general humanoid robots have a torso with a head, two arms and two legs, although some forms of humanoid robots may model only part of the body, for example, from the waist up. Some humanoid robots may also have a 'face', with 'eyes' and 'mouth'.	ALTAI - The Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
	Inference	Inference in AI is when the neural network actually yielding results. More specifically, inference in machine learning is the process of running live data points into a machine learning algorithm (or “ML model”) to calculate an output such as a single numerical score.	https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/pages/altai-assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence
	Interpretability	Interpretability refers to the concept of comprehensibility, explainability, or understandability. When an element of a DTA is interpretable, this means that it is possible at least for an external observer to understand it and find its meaning.	ETAPAS D2.1
IoT	Internet of Things	The internet of things can be understood as an open and extensive network of intelligent objects with the ability to self-organize, exchange information, data, and resources, and respond and act in response to circumstances and changes in the environment.	ALTAI - The Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
	Implicit stereotype	In social identity theory, an implicit bias or implicit stereotype, is the pre-reflective attribution of	https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/pages/altai-

		particular qualities by an individual to a member of some social out group.	assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence"
	Lifecycle	The lifecycle of an AI system includes several interdependent phases ranging from its design and development (including sub-phases such as requirement analysis, data collection, training, testing, and integration), installation, deployment, operation, maintenance, and disposal. Given the complexity of AI (and in general information) systems, several models and methodologies have been defined to manage this complexity, especially during the design and development phases, such as waterfall, spiral, agile software development, rapid prototyping, and incremental.	Toms Project Management Knowledge, accessible at https://project-management-knowledge.com/definitions/f/fallback-plan/
	Malicious surveillance	Surveillance of the users of a system for malicious purposes, e.g. the attacker uses the drone’s video camera to collect information about the target for malicious purposes. Such malice may be inferred from an act done in willful disregard of the rights of another, or an act wrongfully done without just cause or excuse, or an act or omission of duty betraying a willful disregard of social duty.	ALTAI - The Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
-	Management	Management is a process of planning, decision making, organizing, leading, motivation and controlling the human resources, financial, physical, and information resources of an organization to reach its goals efficiently and effectively.	https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/pages/altai-assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence"
	Meaningful human review	Key considerations for meaningful human review from the ICO framework and the European Data Protection Board are: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. human reviewers must be involved in checking the system’s recommendation and should not just apply the automated recommendation to an individual in a routine fashion 2. reviewers’ involvement must be active and not just a token gesture. They should have actual ‘meaningful’ influence on the decision, including the ‘authority and competence’ to go against the recommendation 3. reviewers’ must ‘weigh-up’ and ‘interpret’ the recommendation, consider all available input data, and also take into account other additional factors. 	ICO framework

	Mitigation	Mitigation means reducing risk of loss from the occurrence of any undesirable event by taking certain actions (i.e. mitigation actions). A mitigation action is a specific action, project, activity, or process taken to reduce or eliminate long-term risk to people and property from hazards and their impacts.	https://www.longdom.org/open-access/fault-tolerance-and-techniques.pdf
	Model debugging	Model debugging attempts to test ML models like code and to probe sophisticated ML response functions and decision boundaries to detect and correct accuracy, fairness, security, and other problems in ML systems	ETAPAS consortium
	Model Evasion	Evasion is one of the most common attacks on machine learning models (ML) performed during production. It refers to designing an input, which seems normal for a human but is wrongly classified by ML models. A typical example is to change some pixels in a picture before uploading, so that the image recognition system fails to classify the result.	https://csrc.nist.gov/glossary/term/fit_for_purpose#:~:text=Definition(s)%3A,implementation%2C%20control%2C%20and%20maintenance.
	Model Inversion	Model inversion refers to a kind of attack to AI models, in which the access to a model is abused to infer information about the training data. So, model inversion turns the usual path from training data into a machine-learned model from a one-way one to a two-way one, permitting the training data to be estimated from the model with varying degrees of accuracy. Such attacks raise serious concerns given that training data usually contain privacy-sensitive information.	https://developers.google.com/machine-learning/crash-course/generalization/video-lecture
	Navigation system	A navigation system is an instrument that determines the position of a vehicle and the route to a particular place.	ICO framework
	Omission bias or omitted variable bias	Omission bias occurs when one or more important variables are left out of the model.	ALTAI - The Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
	Open data	Open data is a piece of content or data that is open to anyone and can be used freely, reused, and redistributed. The open data should be accessible, assessable, intelligible and usable, to all users. (https://opendefinition.org/)	https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/pages/altai-assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence "
	Operator	The system operator monitors and controls the operation of the mainframe hardware and software. The operator starts and stops system tasks, monitors the system consoles for unusual conditions, and works with the system programming and production control staff to	ALTAI - The Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence

		ensure the health and normal operation of the systems.	
	Operationalization	Operationalization is the process by which researchers conducting quantitative research spell out precisely how a concept will be measured.	https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/pages/altai-assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence "
	Opt-out	Opt out refers to the choice a human has not to participate in something. If you opt for something, or opt to do something, you choose it or decide to do it in preference to anything else.	https://www.pdpc.gov.sg/-/media/files/pdpc/pdf-files/resource-for-organisation/ai/sgmodelaigovframework2.pdf
	Overfitting	Overfitting, in statistics, is the production of an analysis that corresponds too closely or exactly to a particular set of data, and may therefore fail to fit additional data or predict future observations reliably.	https://www.analyticsinsight.net/humble-ai-influences-decision-making-system/
	Performance metric	Performance metrics are defined as figures and data representative of an organization's actions, abilities, and overall quality. There are many different forms of performance metrics, including sales, profit, return on investment, customer happiness, customer reviews, personal reviews, overall quality, and reputation in a marketplace.	https://www.automate.org/a3-content/service-robots-humanoid-robots
	Personnel	Staff /People that are working directly and interacting with DTAs	
	Pen testing	A penetration test, colloquially known as a pen test, pen test or ethical hacking, is an authorized simulated cyberattack on a computer system, performed to evaluate the security of the system. The test is performed to identify both weaknesses (also referred to as vulnerabilities), including the potential for unauthorized parties to gain access to the system's features and data, as well as strengths, enabling a full risk assessment to be completed.	https://www.sciencedaily.com/terms/humanoid-robot.htm "
	Proxy variable	A variable used instead of the variable of interest when that variable of interest cannot be measured directly.	https://hazelcast.com/glossary/machine-learning-inference/
	Pseudonymisation	Pseudonymisation refers to the idea that it is not possible to attribute personal data to a specific data subject without additional information.	ALTAI - The Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
	Random sampling	Random sampling is a part of the sampling technique in which each sample has an equal probability of being chosen. A sample chosen	https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/pages/altai-assessment-list-

		randomly is meant to be an unbiased representation of the total population	trustworthy-artificial-intelligence"
	Red teaming	A red team is a team that is formed with the objective of subjecting an AI system to rigorous analysis and challenge	Madakam, Ramaswamy, and Tripathi, "Internet of Things (IoT): A Literature Review."
	Regularization methods	Regularization techniques work by limiting the capacity of models—such as neural networks, linear regression, or logistic regression—by adding a parameter norm penalty to the objective function.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Implicit_stereotype
	Relevance, appropriateness, and domain Knowledge	The understanding and utilization of the most appropriate sources and types of data are crucial for building robust and unbiased DTAs. The close collaboration of domain experts with the technical team will assist in the determination of the optimally appropriate categories and sources of measurement.	ALTAI - The Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
	Reliability	An AI system is said to be reliable if it behaves as expected, even for novel inputs on which it has not been trained or tested earlier.	https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/pages/altai-assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence"
	Reproducibility	Reproducibility refers to the closeness between the results of two actions, such as two scientific experiments, that are given the same input and use the methodology, as described in a corresponding scientific evidence (such as a scientific publication). A related concept is replication, which is the ability to independently achieve non-identical conclusions that are at least similar, when differences in sampling, research procedures and data analysis methods may exist. Reproducibility and replicability together are among the main tools of the scientific method.	https://www.lawinsider.com/dictionary/malicious-purpose
	Representativeness	Representativeness refers to the fit between the data collected or procured and the underlying population to be modeled. Underrepresentation or overrepresentation of specific groups is linked to the sampling bias and means of remediation to correct for representational flaws in the sampling should be employed by technical staff.	https://www.iedunote.com/management
	Resiliency	System resilience is an ability of the system to withstand a major disruption within acceptable degradation parameters and to recover within an acceptable time.	ICO framework

	Re-weighting	Weighting is applied to input data that is fed into an artificial neural network to produce related outputs. Re-weighting is where the initial weighting is altered so that it produces a different related output.	https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/definition/mitigation
	Risk	The definitions provided for risk are: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. risk = an unwanted event which may or may not occur. 2. risk = the cause of an unwanted event which may or may not occur. 3. risk = the probability of an unwanted event which may or may not occur. 4. risk = the statistical expectation value of an unwanted event which may or may not occur. 5. risk = the fact that a decision is made under conditions of known probabilities ("decision under risk" as opposed to "decision under uncertainty") 	ICO framework
	Robotics	Robotics, design, construction, and use of machines (robots) to perform tasks done traditionally by human beings. The use of robotics can be very dynamic. Robots can automate various human tasks such as caring for the sick, driving a car, making love, and aid manufacturer workers. As a result, contemporary robotics is very concerned with the impacts that this technology may have when automating such activities.	ALTAI - The Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
	Robustness AI	Robustness of an AI system encompasses both its technical robustness (appropriate in a given context, such as the application domain or life cycle phase) and as well as its robustness from a social perspective (ensuring that the AI system duly takes into account the context and environment in which the system operates). This is crucial to ensure that, even with good intentions, no unintentional harm can occur. Robustness is the third of the three components necessary for achieving Trustworthy AI.	https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/pages/altai-assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence "
	Rogue applications	Rogue applications are fraudulent versions of credible apps made to look like the original versions. Cybercriminals create the apps to gather sensitive information about the users, who believe they're inputting data into reliable software from a brand they already trust.	ALTAI - The Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
RCA	Root cause analysis	Root cause analysis is the process of discovering the root causes of problems in order to identify	https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-

		appropriate solutions. RCA assumes that it is much more effective to systematically prevent and solve for underlying issues rather than just treating ad hoc symptoms and putting out fires. Root cause analysis can be performed with a collection of principles, techniques, and methodologies that can all be leveraged to identify the root causes of an event or trend.	alliance/pages/altai-assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence"
	Social impact assessment	Social impact assessment is described as “the process of identifying the future consequences of a current or proposed action which are related to individuals, organizations and social macro-systems.	https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/navigation-system
	Source integrity & measurement accuracy	Both the sources and instruments of measurement may introduce discriminatory factors into a dataset. Achieving optimal source integrity presupposes that the data gathering processes involved suitable, reliable, and impartial sources of measurement and sound methods of collection.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Omitted-variable bias
	Stability	A stable data is one in which the inputs and conditions are consistent over time. This means the sources of variation are consistent over time, and the data do not exhibit unpredictable variation.	https://opendefinition.org/
	Standards	Standards are norms designed by industry and/or Governments that set product or services’ specifications. They are a key part of our society as they ensure quality and safety in both products and services in international trade. Businesses can be seen to benefit from standards as they can help cut costs by improved systems and procedures put in place. Standards are internationally agreed by experts and they usually represent what the experts think is the best way of doing something. It could be about making a product, managing a process, delivering a service or supplying materials – standards cover a huge range of activities. Standards are released by international organizations, such as ISO (International Organisation for Standardisation), IEEE (The Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers) Standard Association, and NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology)	https://krb-sjobs.brassring.com/TGnewUI/Search/home/HomeWithPreLoad?PageType=JobDetails&partnerid=26059&siteid=5016&jobid=475496
	Statistical accuracy	Broadly, statistical accuracy refers to how often an AI system guesses the correct answer, measured against correctly labelled test data. In many cases, the outputs of an AI system are not intended to be treated as factual information about the individual,	https://scientificinquiryisocialwork.pressbooks.com/chapter/9-3-operationalization/

		but statistically informed guesses as to something which may be true about the individual now or in the future.	
	Stratified Sampling	Stratified sampling is a type of sampling method in which the total population is divided into smaller groups or strata to complete the sampling process.	https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/opt-out
	Sustainable system	A sustainable system is one whose attributes stay within an acceptable range of states.	ICO framework
	Systematic bias	Systematic bias is a bias resulting from the system, leading on average to systematic errors, in contrast to random errors, which on average cancel each other out.	https://avada.io/resources/performance-metrics.html
	Systematic Sampling	Systematic sampling is a type of probability sampling method in which sample members from a larger population are selected according to a random starting point but with a fixed, periodic interval.	ETAPAS consortium
	Third-Party Audit	A third-party audit is performed by an audit organization independent of the customer-supplier relationship and is free of any conflict of interest. Independence of the audit organization is a key component of a third-party audit. Third-party audits may result in certification, registration, recognition, an award, license approval, a citation, a fine, or a penalty issued by the third-party organization or an interested party.	ALTAI - The Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
	Threat	Any circumstance or event with the potential to cause harm to an information system in the form of destruction, disclosure, adverse modification of data, and/or denial of service.	https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/pages/altai-assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence"
	Timeliness and recency	Outdated data may not be able to capture changing social relationships or group dynamics, leading to loss of accuracy with regard to the actual characteristics of the underlying population and thus potentially introducing bias into your AI system. The timeliness and recency of all elements of the data that constitute the datasets should be scrutinized.	https://www.oxfordreference.com/view/10.1093/oi/authority.20110803100351624
	Traceability	Traceability includes the ability to track the journey of a data input through all stages of sampling, labelling, processing and decision making.	ALTAI - The Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
	Transparency	A transparency is some aspect of the distributed system that is hidden from the user (programmer, system developer, and user or application program). A transparency is provided by including some set of mechanisms in the distributed system	https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/pages/altai-assessment-list

		at a layer below the interface where the transparency is required.	trustworthy-artificial-intelligence"
	Trustworthines s	Trustworthiness is the ability to keep promises, to be honest, reliable and principled while never inappropriately betraying a confidence.	https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/definition/random-sampling
	Trustworthy system	Computer hardware, software and procedures that: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. are reasonably secure from intrusion and misuse; 2. provide a reasonable level of availability, reliability, and correct operation 3. are reasonably suited to performing their intended functions 4. adhere to generally accepted security procedures. 	ICO framework
	Trustworthy AI	Trustworthy AI has three components: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. it should be lawful, ensuring compliance with all applicable laws and regulations 2. it should be ethical, demonstrating respect for, and ensure adherence to, ethical principles and values 3. it should be robust, both from a technical and social perspective, since, even with good intentions, AI systems can cause unintentional harm. <p>Trustworthy AI concerns not only the trustworthiness of the AI system itself but also comprises the trustworthiness of all processes and actors that are part of the AI system’s life cycle.</p>	https://heartbeat.fritz.ai/deep-learning-best-practices-regularization-techniques-for-better-performance-of-neural-network-94f978a4e518
	Unstructured data	Unstructured data represents any data that does not have a recognisable structure. It is unorganised and raw and can be non-textual or textual.	https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/earth-and-planetary-sciences/appropriate-technology#:~:text=A%20technology%20is%20deemed%20to,operationally%20controlled%20by%20the%20local
-	User	User refers to the person that makes decision based on DT-application	ALTAI - The Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
-	Use case owner	A person (or group of people) who is responsible for the outcome of a use case. The use case owner can change any aspects of a case and is actively involved in achieving the goals of the case.	https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/pages/altai-assessment-list-

			trustworthy-artificial-intelligence"
	Use case	A use case is a specific situation in which a product or service could potentially be used	ALTAI - The Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
VR	Virtual Reality	Virtual reality is an artificial environment that is created with software and presented to the user in such a way that the user suspends belief and accepts it as a real environment. Virtual reality can enable the wearer to see through various spectral bands, such as infrared, or even download and upgrade the eyeglass prescription that is appropriate for the user's eyes.	https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/pages/altai-assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence"
	Virtual machines or containers	Virtual Machines or containers are emulations of a computer system that run inside, but isolated from the rest of an IT system.	https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2019/624262/EPRS_STU(2019)624262_EN.pdf
	White hat analysis	White hat analysis refers to the analysis conducted with an adversarial mindset to understand where vulnerabilities in an AI system could be. It can be used to detect and counter security vulnerabilities.	https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.7249/j.ctt19w72pw.7?seq=1#metadata_info_tab_contents

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